

STADIEM

STARTUP DRIVEN INNOVATION IN EUROPEAN MEDIA

D4.2 INTEGRATION, PILOTING PHASES AND ASSESSMENT REPORT - THE 1ST CYCLE

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Abstract	This document covers the activities related to the Integrate phase and Pilot phase in the first cycle of the STADIEM Acceleration Programme (March-September 2022), involving the selected start-ups/scale-ups from the first cohort (12 in Integrate, 4 in Pilot). Besides providing a detailed account of the activities, the document contains an assessment of the Phase and identifies lessons learned for the phases during the 2nd cycle in 2023.
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* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

STADIEM is a start-up/scale-up to corporate program aiming to foster the development of next generation internet solutions for the media sector. Its innovation program supports a co-creation trajectory between a start-up and scale-up and a (media) corporate and facilitates the upscaling process of the start-up/scale-up via training, mentorship and showcasing at events. The STADIEM Innovation Program is built in two cycles that each have 4 phases: Match, Develop, Integrate and Pilot. The first cycle ran from April 2021 till September 2022. In this report we present the activities, results and insights of the Integration and Pilot Phases between March 2022 and September 2022. It thus builds upon the previous report that covered these topics for the Match and Develop Phase of the first cycle (see D4.1).

Results and outcomes

For both phases STADIEM managed to achieve the pre-set KPI's. For the Integration Phase, at least 12 beneficiaries from the Develop Phase of the first cycle were selected to enter the Integrate Phase and at the end of the phase at least 12 could integrate on a technical or service level their solution with the corporate in order to be ready for a public pilot. This achievement is demonstrated by the submission of 12 final review reports at the end of the phase as well as their participation in the remote expert evaluation as part of the final selection procedure for the following Pilot Phase. Two of the 12 Integrate beneficiaries declined a selection for the Pilot Phase shortly before the pilot selection meeting of the Investment Committee Board. In the case of OnHertz a bad timing of public piloting within the STADIEM program compared to other plans of both corporate and beneficiary was perceived. Utelly was acquired by another company and lost in this way its status as an SME, which made it ineligible to continue the STADIEM trajectory.

For the Pilot phase OC1, the STADIEM project managed to select and let start 4 beneficiaries from the 10 beneficiaries that declared to candidate for the public pilot phase and at least 4 of them have set up public pilot executions. Due to these public pilots, the four beneficiaries managed to acquire new business leads, investor leads, and client leads. They also participated, besides the STADIEM organised demo-event, at various events ranging from IBC (Tinkerlist boot) to Kinnermet to Fintech Finland (e.g. FilmChain won the trophée at Finnish Fintech pitch event) to also launching media campaigns (Trenition) to showcasing the demo on websites (e.g. Zazu), allowing customers to discover and experiment with the solution.

The exit of Utelly in the Integrate Phase demonstrates the value of STADIEM as a program for the sector. After FanSifter in March 2022, Utelly is the 2nd exit of a beneficiary. In both cases, the beneficiaries testified that STADIEM's support and development opportunities were crucial steps in the process towards the exit.

Besides these two exits, the overall result of the first cycle of the STADIEM Innovation Program at the end of September 2022 is that for each 4 phases all KPI's of minimum participation at the beginning of the phase and minimum selection at the end of the phase were always met. A breach of cooperation between a corporate and a beneficiary never happened during a phase and during the entire first cycle of the program.

Budget and grant distribution

The foreseen budget was in both phases almost consumed totally (99% in the case of Integration; 100% in the case of Piloting) by the start-up and scale-ups.

Running the program and providing upscaling support

On an operational level, we see that the project managed to organise two qualitative cycles. The program framework had in both phases an intense rhythm, which allowed to keep a steady pace in the innovation track and enabled the start-up/scale-up to engage his corporate in the process. The four mother hubs provided the necessary support and mentoring based on individual needs of the beneficiaries and facilitated leads in their networks. Training in the Integration Phase was organised at the beginning of the Phase to let the beneficiaries be fully aware of the importance of the activity and the result to be achieved. During the pilot phase STADIEM organised events to showcase the demos of the 4 final beneficiaries (Future Week) and provide other opportunities for demonstrating the solutions (IBC2022). Besides these STADIEM events, the four pilot beneficiaries also took themselves initiatives with their grant to showcase their solution at relevant venues in Europe.

Learnings and future perspective

While the STADIEM Innovation Program thus generated qualitative results both in terms of outcomes and in terms of running the program, this does not mean that there are no lessons to be learned to improve the program for the 2nd Cycle.

The Integrate phase of the second open call had several opportunities for improvement in four categories: timeline, training, finances, and evaluation of the start-ups. The Integrate phase was too short, leading to an intensive period for the start-ups, hubs, and consortium, while there was an overlap with another phase of cycle 2 (open call/match). The start-ups had limited time for training, and deviations in spending were expected in the next cycle. Feedback from external experts helped improve the evaluation process and reporting procedures for a more efficient process in the next cycle but should also be prepared in advance in order to streamline it better.

The pilot phase of the program worked well overall, but there are opportunities for improvement in the next cycle, such as streamlining the reporting process and starting the Pilot Phase Proposal earlier. The timing of the pilot phase during the holiday season is less than ideal and organizing events to showcase the start-ups' products was challenging. Managing two phases of two different cycles at the same time is also a challenge, but this was less imposing during the pilot phase due to a smaller number of start-ups.

These lessons will be incorporated mainly in the 2nd cycle of the Integration and Pilot Phase. To prepare the ground for this work, preparatory meetings have already been organised within the STADIEM consortium (Hamburg, August 2022 and online, November 2022).

To fully cover both phases and to include a thorough reflection of both phases, the due date of this deliverable D4.2 was delayed from its initial submission in September 2022 (M24) to November 2022 (M26).

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. INTRODUCTION.....	9
2. INTEGRATE PHASE	10
2.1 DESCRIPTIONS AND OBJECTIVES.....	12
2.2 FRAMEWORK.....	13
2.2.1 <i>Overview of the timeline</i>	13
2.2.2 <i>Evaluation process</i>	15
2.2.2 <i>Needs-based support</i>	16
2.2.3 <i>Upskilling and training</i>	17
2.2.4 <i>Networking/showcasing events</i>	18
2.3 BUDGET AND REIMBURSEMENT	18
2.4 KPI'S AND RESULT	19
2.5 DEVIATIONS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS.....	20
2.6 LEARNINGS.....	20
3. PILOT PHASE	23
A. 3.1 DESCRIPTION AND OBJECTIVES	23
3.2 PILOT FRAMEWORK.....	24
3.2.1 <i>Overview of timeline</i>	24
3.2.2 <i>Needs-based support and follow-up</i>	25
3.2.3 <i>Networking and showcasing activities</i>	25
3.2.4 <i>Upskilling and training</i>	27
3.2.5 <i>Evaluation process</i>	28
3.3 BUDGET AND REIMBURSEMENT	30
3.4 KPI'S AND RESULTS.....	31
3.5 DEVIATIONS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS.....	32
3.6 LEARNINGS.....	32
4. CONCLUSIONS.....	34
ANNEX I – TEMPLATE PROPOSAL INTEGRATE TO PILOT	36
ANNEX II – INTEGRATE FRAMEWORK	42
ANNEX III – EVALUATION SURVEY INTEGRATE PHASE.....	47
ANNEX IV – MID-TERM TEMPLATE QUESTIONS INTEGRATE	57
ANNEX V – FINAL REVIEW COST CLAIM QUESTIONS INTEGRATE	59
ANNEX VI – TEMPLATE INTEGRATE TO PILOT PROPOSAL.....	60
APPENDIX VI – PILOT FRAMEWORK	66
APPENDIX VII: MID-TERM REPORT PILOT (AIRTABLE).....	73
APPENDIX VIII: FINAL REVIEW REPORT PILOT PHASE (AIRTABLE)	79

LIST OF TABLES

TABLE 1: OVERVIEW INTEGRATE PHASE - 1ST CYCLE STADIEM INNOVATION PROGRAM	10
TABLE 2: PARTICIPANTS INTEGRATION PHASE - CYCLE 1 STADIEM INNOVATION PROGRAM	12
TABLE 3: ALLOCATION INTEGRATE PARTICIPANTS OVER MOTHER HUBS - 1STE CYCLE STADIEM INNOVATION PROGRAM	14
TABLE 4: TIMELINE INTEGRATION PHASE - 1ST CYCLE STADIEM INNOVATION PROGRAM	15
TABLE 5: OVERVIEW NEEDS-BASED SUPPORT INTEGRATE PHASE - 1ST CYCLE STADIEM INNOVATION PROGRAM	17
TABLE 6: OVERVIEW INSTALMENTS AND GRANT DISTRIBUTION INTEGRATE PHASE - 1ST CYCLE STADIEM INNOVATION PROGRAM	19
TABLE 7: OVERVIEW PILOT PHASE - 1ST CYCLE STADIEM INNOVATION PROGRAM	23
TABLE 8: PARTICIPANTS PILOT PHASE - 1ST CYCLE STADIEM INNOVATION PROGRAM	24
TABLE 9: OVERVIEW EVALUATION PROCESS ACTIVITIES PILOT PHASE - 1ST CYCLE STADIEM INNOVATION PROGRAM	25
TABLE 10: OVERVIEW OF NEEDS-BASED SUPPORT ACTIVITIES PILOT PHASE - 1ST CYCLE STADIEM INNOVATION PROGRAM	25
TABLE 11: OVERVIEW STADIEM ORGANIZED SHOWCASING AND NETWORKING ACTIVITIES PILOT PHASE - 1ST CYCLE STADIEM INNOVATION PROGRAM	25
TABLE 12: DESCRIPTION NEEDS-BASED SUPPORT ACTIVITIES PILOT PHASE - 1ST CYCLE STADIEM INNOVATION PROGRAM	25
TABLE 13: DESCRIPTION STADIEM ORGANIZED SHOWCASING AND NETWORKING ACTIVITIES PILOT PHASE - 1ST CYCLE STADIEM INNOVATION PROGRAM	27
TABLE 14: DESCRIPTION EVALUATION PROCESS ACTIVITIES PILOT PHASE - 1ST CYCLE STADIEM INNOVATION PROGRAM	30
TABLE 15: OVERVIEW BUDGET AND GRANT DISTRIBUTION PILOT PHASE - 1ST CYCLE STADIEM INNOVATION PROGRAM	31
TABLE 16: OVERVIEW LEADS GENERATED BY BENEFICIARIES IN PILOT PHASE - 1STE CYCLE STADIEM INNOVATION PROGRAM	32

ABBREVIATIONS

AB	Advisory Board (Board of experts that provides advice to the STADIEM consortium)
IBC	International Broadcasting Convention (Major media industry event in Europe)
ICB	Investment Committee Board (Board consisting of a representative of each of the 4 STADIEM hubs and 3 external independent evaluators; at the end of each phase the board evaluates pitches and selects the participants for the next phase in the STADIEM Innovation Program)
LOI	Letter of Intent (Document that provides an intent of a media corporate to collaborate with a scale-up/start-up participating in the STADIEM Innovation Program)
MCB	Media City Bergen (One of the 4 hubs in the STADIEM consortium)
NMA	New Media Accelerator (One of the 4 hubs in the STADIEM consortium)
VRT	Vlaamse Radio-en Televisieomroep (One of the 4 hubs in the STADIEM consortium)
STK	Storytek (One of the 4 hubs in the STADIEM consortium)
WP	Work package

1. INTRODUCTION

WP4 '*STADIEM Program*' delivers the STADIEM Innovation Program in its four phases: Match, Develop, Integrate and Pilot. The integrate and Pilot phase are the last two phases in the STADIEM programme (WP4), being Task 4.3 '*Integrate*' and Task 4.4 '*Pilot*'. They follow the first two phases of the programme, the Match phase and the Develop phase, which were covered in D4.1 '*Match and, Develop phases report and assessment report - the 1st cycle*'.

WP4 STADIEM programme builds upon the framework to deliver the programme that has been developed in WP2 '*STADIEM incubation and acceleration framework*' and follows the selection of 40 start-ups in WP3 '*Engaging Startups/SMEs*'. This report, D4.2 '*Integration, Piloting Phases and Assessment Report*' covers all activities related to the Integration and Pilot phases of the first cycle of the STADIEM acceleration program between May 2022 and September 2022. The actions of the four hubs - NMA, ST, VRT and MCB - and the selected start-ups for the phases will be described, including all activities and results of the evaluation periods. The goal of this report is to demonstrate the main outcomes and results and to reflect on the two phases to provide lessons for the 2nd cycle.

The deliverable is structured around two main chapters. Chapter 2 presents the Integration Phase, Chapter 3 the Pilot Phase. Both chapters have the same outline in 6 sections. Section 1 is a description of the phase with a presentation of the participants and the objectives. Section two provides a presentation of the phase framework for the 1st cycle, including an overview of the timeline, an overview of the training and upskilling activities, the evaluation and selection process and the organised networking and showcasing events. Section 3 presents the budget rules and the total amount of reimbursements requested by the beneficiaries compared to the total grant available in the phase. Section 4 discusses the KPI's and results achieved while section 5 presents any deviation from the phase planning and any corrective action taken. Finally, Section 6 highlights lessons learned and suggests improvement opportunities for both phases during the 2nd cycle of STADIEM.

In order to fully cover both phases in this report and to include a thorough reflection of both phases, the due date of this deliverable D4.2 was delayed from its initial submission in September 2022 to November 2022.

2. INTEGRATE PHASE

The Integrate Phase corresponds to Task T4.3 and was led and coordinated by Storytek. The Phase lasted three months, from March to May 2022.

Task	Name	Lead	Contributing Partners	Timing
T4.3	Integrate	Storytek	VRT, NMA, MCB	March - May 2022

TABLE 1: OVERVIEW INTEGRATE PHASE - 1ST CYCLE STADIEM INNOVATION PROGRAM

From the 16 STADIEM beneficiaries that started the previous Develop Phase and submitted an application for the Integrate Phase, 12 beneficiaries with their solution and STADIEM project with a corporate were selected for the Integrate Phase:

Start-up	STADIEM Project	Corporate Partner(s)	Mother hub
Aiconix	Develop a supporting model for automatic speech recognition (ASR) that better supports ASR for regional language varieties. Specifically, within STADIEM's Develop Phase an Austrian dialect model was trained	ORF, APA, Austrian Parliament, Russmedia	NMA
Datavillage	Provide a privacy-preserving personal data platform that enables a personalized content discovery experience across any media service based on the collection of user behavioural data from other digital media channels. In STADIEM Datavillage let users explore content within one channel of a broadcaster based on user preferences created through data produced on other channels such as spotify, youtube, ..	RTBF VRT	VRT
Filmchain	Develops a modular, scalable solution for the automated generation of royalties management calculation and dissemination of royalty reports. In STADIEM its new enterprise solution is developed and tested with a film distributor	Alamode Filmdistribution	STK
Frameright	Combines Image Display Control technology with a novel AI model to guarantee the correct	Frankfurter Allgemeine	STK

	image display and other visual material on many digital channels. Within STADIEM the focus is on developing a IDC - solution that fosters credible visual journalism	Zeitung	
OnHertz	OnHertz will co-develop with the corporate a hybrid (on premises/cloud) distributed live production platform (audio/video) that integrates within the current production backbone. The platform will enable the operational teams of the corporate to produce live shows (audio/video) from anywhere at any time without having to think about the physical location of resources.	RTBF	MCB
The Chainless	Developed In Stadiem structured knowledge will be added to the solution in the forms of knowledge graph and hence increase the performance of AI-aided video and image classification, supporting archiving, creating added value for media documentation, archiving and retrieval for several use cases.	ProSiebenSat1	NMA
Tinkerlist	Developed an online scripting and rundown tool - One Man Band - that allows media creators of live tv, radio and online shows to develop content and manage their workflow. In STADIEM the solution is further developed, user researched and upscaled to a full innovative software tool	DPG/VRT	VRT
Trenstion	Trenstion's trendtracker is AI-driven strategic intelligence platform that supports an automated, cost-efficient and continues way to track trends. Within STADIEM the tool will be developed as a SAAS tool that media companies can use as a go-to tool to monitor and analyse trends and support strategic planning	Roularta Media Group/SWR	NMA
Utelly	Developed a SAAS- content discovery platform using advanced AI techniques that aggregates content and make it more discoverable for users and producers. In STADIEM Utelly will further develop it solution focusing on TV by including other media types (print, media, podcasts) and other metadata sources	Roularta Media Group	MCB

Visualyst	Supports video creators and distributors to perform comprehensive editorial compliance reviews through AI-assisted discovery and cloud collaboration. In Stadiem the focus is on two processes: specific brand detection in video and detection of background textual elements relating to hate speech and bad language	Telia Norway/PBS America	MCB
Web64	Developed a real time data tool providing insights that allows newsmakers to understand what content is consumed, where it is shared and who is publishing it. Within STADIEM the collaboration with the corporate allowed to implement new features and develop new modules that better serve the needs of newsmakers, among others making the solution relevant for factcheckers	VRT	VRT
Zazu	A B2B-tool to create, monitor and distribute stories (vertical content) across all platforms and every part of the customer journey from the social media to websites. Within STADIEM, two functionalities have been developed - content automation (automatic article to story automation) and Mobile SDK	Roularta Media Group	STK

TABLE 2: PARTICIPANTS INTEGRATION PHASE - CYCLE 1 STADIEM INNOVATION PROGRAM

2.1 DESCRIPTIONS AND OBJECTIVES

The 12 start-ups/scale-ups which were able to successfully complete the Develop Phase and were selected to proceed in the STADIEM Innovation Program entered, after having accepted the invitation, the Integration Phase. The overall objective of the Integration Phase is that the STADIEM beneficiaries finalize the (technical/procedural) integration of the solution and prepare for public piloting planning with the corporate. This includes internal testing and an evaluation of the business processes, performance, technologies, and solutions with a corporate partner.

STADIEM has from its outset decided to put particular emphasis on the Integration phase before the testing and validation. The Integration Phase is considered as a risk-mitigation measure for the Pilot Phase. The importance and complexity of integration is often forgotten, which could negatively affect the results of the testing. In a Program such as STADIEM the risk can be situated at both parties (start-up/scale-up and corporate). By planning an Integration phase before piloting, slow process structure within a large corporation does not have to interfere with the piloting and testing of the

startup's project, but can be dissolved prior. Through this preparational step, the Pilot Phase can then completely focus on the pilot and the frame is set to test and validate the startups project for the corporate.

The length of the Integration Phase is 2 months, which is shorter than the other 3 phases. Therefore events, support and training activities are organised in a different way than in the other phases, as will be explained below in more detail.

For this part of the pan-European acceleration program all participating start-ups get a timeframe of 2 months and a maximum of 27.000€.

2.2 FRAMEWORK

2.2.1 Overview of the timeline

The Integrate Phase kicked off with an onboarding meeting on 14th March 2022 where all 12 participating beneficiaries were informed about the expected outcomes, the processes, and the deadlines for the Phase. The Integrate Framework document (see Annex II) was afterwards shared with them via STADIEM's Airtable that was tested as the project management tool towards start-ups (cfr. D2.3 for a description)

From that moment onwards integration work was officially launched, and beneficiaries had to work on them during the whole two months. Besides the daily operations to integrate and pre-plan piloting between beneficiary and corporate, there were specific interactions with the STADIEM hubs to provide support and guidance, monitor progress and evaluate.

Each of the 12 beneficiaries was assigned to a mother hub (3 for each hub), according to the best match of the hub regarding expertise and network to support the beneficiary. The mother hubs assisted with coaching, follow-up, and served as the main point of contact for each start-up/scale-up throughout the entirety of the Phase.

Stadium Integrate Beneficiary	Motherhub
Aiconix	NMA
Datavillage	VRT
Filmchain	Storytek
Frameright	Storytek
On Hertz	MCB
The Chainless	NMA
Tinkerlist	VRT
Trenstion	NMA

Utelly	MCB
Visualyst	MCB
Web64	VRT
Zazu-Cutnut	Storytek

TABLE 3: ALLOCATION INTEGRATE PARTICIPANTS OVER MOTHER HUBS - 1STE CYCLE STADIEM INNOVATION PROGRAM

After the onboarding meeting, the beneficiaries had to deliver their Develop to Integrate Plan by 25th March 2022 (see Annex I for template)). This plan detailed specifically for the Integration Phase the objectives and ambitions (product, client, targets, KPI's, challenges), the pathway to generate impact (action plan, outcomes, scale and significance of outcomes) and the concrete implementation of the actions (budget, personal, timeline, training, risk mitigation).

On the 25th of March 2022 the 12 beneficiaries had to attend an Integrate Panel Session where they could hear testimonies of CTO's and top Integrators on Integration and could ask questions and feedback (cfr 2.2.3 upskilling and training).

Mid-April, halfway through the Integration phase, a mid-term review took place in preparation for the final evaluation (Annex IV). During the mid-term-review, the start-ups' progress in relation to the original needs, objectives and action plan were checked during a light check-in talk with the mother hub. The start-ups had to present:

- An overview of the implementation of the activities performed in the phase including resource spending;
- An overview of impact activities highlighting the actual impact of the co-creation on both start-up and corporate;
- And overview of risk, especially considering the impact to the corporate;
- An overview of needs or requests to the mother hub, and/or the consortium.

The mother hub provided feedback and, if necessary, mitigation suggestions. After the mid-term check-in, the beneficiaries had to upload in STADIEM Airtable the information provided above via an online questionnaire (Annex IV) as well as provide an overview of the budget spendings and proofs.

From the 2nd week of May 2022 onwards, the evaluation period of the Integration Phase took off. Start-up and Corporate had to complete individually each a question list (see evaluation section for more details, Annex III), followed by a check-in with the mother hub between 09-13 May and finally a pitch before the Investment Committee Board on the 25th of May. This led ultimately to the selection of 4 STADIEM beneficiaries for the final Pilot stage (see Chapter 3). Also a final cost claim and final review form had to be completed (Annex V).

Activity	Date	Description
Onboarding meeting and briefing	14th March 2022	1 joint meeting with the 4 hubs and the 12 selected start-ups; briefing of expected outcomes, processes and deadlines and updated Phase Plan
Submission Develop to Integrate Plan	25th March	Submission of the Develop to Integrate Phase Plan via Airtable
Expert Panel on Integration	25th March	online panel discussion and Q&A with top Integrators and CTO's
Mid-term check-in meeting	11-15 april 2022	1 meeting per start-up with their mother hub to discuss their progress of the first half of the Develop Phase
Final review meeting	09-13 May 2022	1 meeting per start-up with their mother hub to discuss their progress of the second half of the Develop Phase
Investment Committee Board	25 May 2022	1 joint meeting with the 4 hubs, the 12 selected start-ups and the Investment Committee members. Presentation by start-up (pitch/demo) Evaluation and ranking based on corporate assessment and pitch / demo
Announcement Final Decision	26 May 2022	Decision of selection/ non-selection for Pilot Phase sent to the Integrate beneficiaries

TABLE 4: TIMELINE INTEGRATION PHASE - 1ST CYCLE STADIEM INNOVATION PROGRAM

2.2.2 Evaluation process

Requirements

The start-ups/scale-ups must fulfil the following requirements:

- An action and budget plan for the stage at the start of the phase.
- A definition of the funding/upskilling for the Phase.
- A project plan for a publicly accessible and evaluable pilot including budget, and pilot readiness checklist with risk assessment.
- The plan must meet the needs of the Corporate and the Corporate validates the readiness for publicly accessible and evaluable Pilot (via a written evaluation form).
- An assessment of the plan for the next phase (Pilot phase).

Documentation

The documentation received at the end of the phase should include but is not limited to the following:

- Internal testing and evaluation of **business processes and performance**, technologies, and solutions that enable and drive forward the start-up and corporate collaboration;
- Documentation of the integration and collaboration procedures, including integration and pilot roadmap, APIs, testing and pilot scoping documentation and evaluation (if relevant);
- Detailed description of test and pilot cases(s);
- Corporate validation to the proposed activities with clearly identified and comprehensible feedback about the pilot and its impact and implementation on behalf of the corporate.

Selection and evaluation process

The final evaluation of this Phase will follow three intertwined steps:

1. submission of a project plan for the next phase;
2. submission of a written evaluation and confirmation for the public pilot by the Corporate in the form of an evaluation form;
3. pitching session for the STADIEM Investment Committee consisting of at least 3 independent experts and 1 representative per STADIEM Hub.

Thereafter the Investment Committee then formally approves a list of the top-ranked proposals. At least 4 out of the 12 start-ups will be selected for the Pilot phase. Meeting the criteria does not automatically result in being selected.

2.2.2 Needs-based support

Since it was decided to keep this phase as light as possible to allow the start-ups full range to focus on their integration processes, the traditional combination of a mid-term report and a meeting with the start-up and their mother hub were condensed in a single mid-term light check-in per start-up, without having to issue a written report about the first half of the phase. These meetings were appointed between the 18th and the 22nd, April 2022 and consisted in a 60 min to 90 min one-to-one with each mother hub.

Besides these mid-term check-ins, start-ups were advised to communicate their needs for businesses' or investor's introductions from their mother hubs or another hub from STADIEM. It was also the case in the two previous phases of the programme and was not specific to the Integrate Phase.

Activity	Timing	Approach
Check-ins	By appointment	Individual check-in meetings between start-up and mother hub Depending on start-ups needs
Business introductions	By appointment	Demand-based + cross-hub approach
Investor meetings	By appointment	Demand-based + cross-hub approach

TABLE 5: OVERVIEW NEEDS-BASED SUPPORT INTEGRATE PHASE - 1ST CYCLE STADIEM INNOVATION PROGRAM

2.2.3 Upskilling and training

On the 25th of March 2022 a special CTO panel “Ask me anything” with Jordan Valdma was organized.

Since the Integrate phase on-boarding meeting was on 14th March this activity was set very early in the phase. Each start-up was asked to prepare questions about the Integration phase to ask to the CTO. Questions were gathered by Storytek in advance to moderate the meeting. This date coincided with their deadline to provide an action plan: it allowed the participants to make sure they were starting the phase with the appropriate questions and challenges in mind, particularly how to strengthen their business case with an expert’s input. The meeting was remote and set as a 120 min “Ask me Anything”. It allowed the founders to get more tailored answers in a collective meeting and compare experiences with their fellow start-ups. It also gave them the opportunity to ask for specific issues that they were facing and that required an external and expert’s point of view.

This activity was set very early to alleviate workload during the shortest phase of the programme (2 months) and to set goals between the start-ups and their corporate to improve their integration plan or pivot if necessary: the start-ups were also mostly in seed stage when they entered STADIEM, so they needed more guidance and training than anticipated to lead a successful pilot. It needed to be achieved as early as possible in the programme.

The guest CTO was Jordan Valdma: Tallinn based co-founder and CEO of Producement (IT Services and IT Consulting) and former CTO of several start-ups in various fields, including Salv (financial services) and Challenger Bank. The biggest asset of this activity was having a guest with a long and successful experience as a founder himself, to give hands-on feedback on how to build a successful solution, but also how to build a strong business case, how to scale-up, de-risk or how to invest in experts to straighten their company's sustainability.

Lastly, the founders were also able to ask for 1 to 1 meetings and specific contacts for various types of counselling (legal, cybersecurity etc).

In total 21 collaborators from the STADIEM Integrate Phase beneficiaries participated. The feedback from the participants was overall very positive and the meeting was qualified as very informative.

2.2.4 Networking/showcasing events

Given the short time span of the Integration Phase (2 months), the importance of performing a good Integration exercise with the corporate and the COVID-19 measures that were in place as well as the fact that the next stage of the Program focuses on public piloting, the STADIEM consortium believed it was better to let the beneficiaries focus on their Integration work and pre-planning of public pilots. Therefore, no STADIEM event that involved (a part of) the twelve beneficiaries to network with or to showcase them to broader ecosystems were organised in this period.

2.3 BUDGET AND REIMBURSEMENT

For this part of the pan-European acceleration program all participating start-ups/scale-ups get a timeframe of 2 months and a maximum grant of 27.500€.

At the beginning of the Phase an Integrate Phase proposal was submitted with a budget for the phase. The proposed budget had to mirror the start-up's acceleration and actual needs (i.e. upskilling, integration or piloting costs) in light of STADIEM and the Integrate Phase. The budget could be spent on:

- Engaging specialists / advisors / personnel to guarantee successful co-creation with the corporate, to more effectively manage integration and piloting etc...;
- Improving the value proposition or product/solution fit which would increase the value that is brought to the media partner;
- Hard investment in R&D;
- Developing additional capacities;
- Following workshops and training.

During the Integrate Phase, it will be possible to revise the budget considering actual progress during the Phase, but always in collaboration with and upon approval of the mother hub.

The beneficiary was paid 30% of its Integrate Phase budget of €27.500 upfront at the beginning of the Integrate Phase. When a start-up's Integrate budget exceeds the maximum allowed €27.500 for this phase, the calculation will be of the maximum allowed grant (27.500€).

The remaining part was reimbursed in 2 following instalments based on actual deliverables with financial reporting and meeting KPI's midway the phase (mid-term review) and at the end of the phase (final review). For the mid-term and final review, the start-ups had to deliver a progress report including a financial review indicating costs and expenditures with proof and legitimations.

The payment depended on the positive assessment of the start-up's/scale-up's Integrate Phase activities. After assessment and acceptance of the progress report by the STADIEM hubs (Annex IV and Annex V), the necessary steps for reimbursement will be taken, following VRT's rules for reimbursement. If start-up does not meet the Phase's expectations or shows signs of negligence, reimbursement will be adjusted accordingly or cancelled altogether.

The grant of 27.500€ was, according to the Sub-Grant Agreement and the Guide for Applicants, distributed during the Integration Phase in three stages (cfr Develop Phase): 30% of the total grant at the beginning of the phase, 35% after mid-term review and financial report and 35% after final review and financial report.

The table below shows the distribution of the budget according to the GA and Guide for Applicants OC1 and the actual distribution based on the Integrate Phase Proposal (Payment 1) and the financial reports at mid-term (Payment 2) and at final review (Payment 3). It shows that the 12 beneficiaries in total consumed **326.226** euro, hence, **99** % of the foreseen total grant of 330.000 euro.

	Payment 1 30%	Payment 2 35%	Payment 3 35%	Total Integrate Period
GA	99.000€	115.500€	115.500€	330.000€
Actual 3rd Party Payment	98.522,7€	114.943,15€	112.760€	326.226€
Difference GA - Actual 3rd Party Payment	477,3€	556,85€	112.760€	3774€

TABLE 6: OVERVIEW INSTALMENTS AND GRANT DISTRIBUTION INTEGRATE PHASE - 1ST CYCLE STADIEM INNOVATION PROGRAM

2.4 KPI'S AND RESULT

The main KPI of the Integrate OC1 Phase, according to the GA is to have at least 12 beneficiaries to start the phase and to assure that “*at least 12 start-ups finalize technical or service level integration with corporations to conduct public pilots per open call (total at least 24)*”.

For the Integrate OC1 phase, we highlighted above in the presentation of the Phase the 12 selected beneficiaries out of the 16 that participated in the end evaluation of the Develop Phase OC1. At the end of the Integration Phase, STADIEM received the final review reports from the 12 beneficiaries, each making sure that they were ready for public piloting. All 12 beneficiaries also participated in the remote expert evaluation that is part of the final review. This means that 12 technical or service level integrations with the corporates were conducted to be ready for public piloting.

Before the Investment Committee Board pitches of 25th May, STADIEM received an official writing from beneficiaries Utelly and OnHertz that they would withdraw from the STADIEM Program after the Integration Phase. In the case of Utelly this was because the company was being purchased on 25th May 2022 by Synamedia. For the OnHertz STADIEM project, the corporate RTBf (French speaking public broadcaster in Belgium) and the beneficiary concluded that the overall planning of STADIEM was no longer aligned anymore with the planning of both the beneficiary and the corporate need for the product development.

On a more general outcome level of the project, the news about Utelly means that it was the 2nd time (after FanSifter in the Develop Phase OC1) that STADIEM support and involvement led to an exit for a start-up/scale-up.

2.5 DEVIATIONS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS

The main deviations during the Integrate phase occurred due to a need for adaptation to changes caused by an external factor, Covid-19. Lack of traveling, sick leaves etc. resulted in small delays that did not fundamentally impact the Phase program and could be dealt with.

2.6 LEARNINGS

During the Integrate phase of the second open call several opportunities for improvement were spotted. They belong to four categories: timeline, training, finances, and evaluation of the start-ups.

Timeline

The Integrate phase is the shortest in the program, lasting only for 2 months, which results in an extremely intensive period for integration, phase management and

evaluating the start-ups at the end of the phase. Moreover, in 2022, there was an overlap between the Open Call and Match Phase of OC2 and the Integrate phase of OC1. This puts an extra burden on an already time-intensive phase. For the hubs, three challenges were constantly present during the Integration Phase: managing a heavy workload for each hub, guaranteeing an effective decision-making process in a fast-changing environment and coping with short time spans to organise events with mentors. For start-ups and scale-ups, the short period means working hard to integrate solutions while also finding the necessary time to complete reports and attend meetings with corporates or the consortium. While the consortium could mitigate the risks and the integration phase was implemented according to plan, the following actions are needed to reduce the time pressure for the Integration Phase of the 2nd cohort:

- Prepare the Integration Phase early on in the Development Phase;
- Preparation and information to start-ups about the Integration Phase should not start at the onboarding meeting, but after mid-term of Develop phase;
- Continue the usage of the STADIEM toolkit on Airtable and further develop it with the following features;
- optimizing the timing and repartition of tasks ahead: due deliverables, meetings, data gathering and analysis;
- anticipate and align with the corporate timeline, after noticing a slower pace than the start-ups' and longer delays for decision making during the OC1, to improve the communication and prevent risks.

Some of the accompanying actions have already been launched and implemented and will be reported on in more detail in deliverable D4.4 in M36 (September 2023) that will describe and assess the Integration Phase of the 2nd Open Call. In anticipation of this deliverable, we like to already mention that:

- the consortium dedicated a special meeting on Integration during the Hub meeting in Hamburg and during a special consortium meeting in November 2022;
- on 15/12 (2 months before the launch of Integrate Phase OC2) a meeting with the 16 beneficiaries of the Develop OC2 was organized to inform them about the broad lines of the upcoming Integrate Phase OC2;
- corporates were briefed 21/12/2022.

Training

The start-ups have very little time during the Integrate phase stage to get training, either offered by the consortium or self-paid. In the impact analysis research, STADIEM learned that start-ups which requested learning and training support (also paid ones) tended to perform better.

It has been notified to the OC2 start-ups to raise attendance during events like Training Tuesdays early on. The phase is late in the program. Feedback was also gathered from the OC1 training sessions to accommodate the start-ups' needs for a successful pilot and learn lessons from unexpected responses.

Finances

During the Impact assessment preparation (March - April - May 2022) and after the Integrate phase, feedback was gathered regarding the phase spendings to adapt and improve the support to the start-ups for the OC2. Modifications and adaptations are expected in the OC2.

Evaluation process

The external experts who were mandated to review the start-ups' reports were followed up by a meeting to get feedback. They considered the process "very good" and helped suggest cuts to shorten the questionnaire, as well as simplifications to optimize the evaluation process and reporting procedures for more efficient evaluations during the OC2. It will result in a simplified and more efficient process.

3. PILOT PHASE

The Pilot Phase corresponds to Task T4.4 'Pilot' and was led and coordinated by Media City Bergen. The Phase in the first cycle lasted four months, from May to September 2022.

Task N°	Title	Lead	Contributing Partners	Timing
4.4	Pilot	MCB	NMA, STK, VRT	M21-M34

TABLE 7: OVERVIEW PILOT PHASE - 1ST CYCLE STADIEM INNOVATION PROGRAM

A. 3.1 DESCRIPTION AND OBJECTIVES

In the fourth and final phase of the STADIEM programme, the Pilot Phase, the four top performing start-ups from the Integrate phase are invited to join and pilot their solution. During the Pilot phase the start-ups execute public pilots with the corporates in real-life environments, demonstrating their results and achievements from their STADIEM project at a large scale to a wider community of stakeholders. The pilots are evaluated for generating business value and gathering feedback from customers and other involved parties.

The Pilot Phase has a duration of four months, where the first cycle started the phase in June 2022 and finished September 2022. Each beneficiary in the Pilot Phase can receive a maximum of € 50.000 in funding support from the STADIEM consortium during the Pilot Phase. In the first cycle, the beneficiaries of the Pilot Phase were Zazu, Tinkerlist, Filmchain, and Trensition:

Start-up	Project which was piloted	Corporate Partner(s)	Mother hub in the Pilot Phase
Zazu	a software development kit for story content automation and mobile integration possibilities	Roularta Media Group	MCB
Tinkerlist	an online and/or breaking news set	VRT and DPG Media	VRT
Filmchain	a modular, scalable solution for the automated generation and dissemination of royalty reports	Alamode Filmdistribution	STK
Trensition	a strategic analytics platform with tailored targets	Roularta Media Group and SWR	NMA

TABLE 8: PARTICIPANTS PILOT PHASE - 1ST CYCLE STADIEM INNOVATION PROGRAM

3.2 PILOT FRAMEWORK

3.2.1 Overview of timeline

The Pilot Phase started off with a hybrid onboarding meeting, showcasing event, and mingling event in Bergen, Norway, with three of the start-ups being present in Bergen and one participating and presenting digitally. During the onboarding meeting, the four start-ups of the phase were invited to get a briefing of the phase's framework (see Annex VI), including its expected outcomes, processes, important dates and deadlines. Shortly thereafter, the start-ups submitted their proposal for the Pilot Phase, detailing their plans and objectives for the phase.

At the very start of the phase, the start-ups were allocated to each own's mother hub. As in previous phases, the mother hubs assisted the start-up throughout the phase with coaching and follow-up and served as their main point of contact in the STADIEM consortium. The start-ups main activity in the Pilot Phase was to execute public pilots in collaboration with their corporate partner(s). They also had to demonstrate their pilot to a wider audience, including prospects similar to the corporate partner, and participate in conferences and events, meet with potential users, and disseminate the results of the project. And for those looking for funding, they also were to pitch to investors and corporates to collect interest.

Halfway through the phase the start-ups met with their mother hub for a mid-term review, closely followed by the start-ups submitting a mid-term financial report. For the end-of-phase evaluation, the start-ups had to submit a final report, covering their assessment, results, and progress in the phase, as well as their spending. They also presented their results and achievements in a final Investment Committee Meeting, alongside their corporate partners, in front of a board made up by the hubs and three external experts.

To finish off the Phase and to again showcase the pilots, there was organized for the start-ups to attend IBC (International Broadcasting Convention) and exhibit their pilots at the STADIEM pods.

Activity	Time
Onboarding Event	7 June
Submittal of Pilot Phase Proposal	10 June
Mid-term Review Meeting	18-22 July
Mid-term Financial Review	22 July
Evaluation Period	September
Submittal of Evaluation Report Part 1	15 September
Investment Committee Meeting	28 September
Submittal of Evaluation Report Part 2	3 October

TABLE 9: OVERVIEW EVALUATION PROCESS ACTIVITIES PILOT PHASE - 1ST CYCLE STADIEM INNOVATION PROGRAM

Activity	Time
Status Meetings	By appointment
Business Introductions	By appointment
Investor Meetings	By appointment

TABLE 10: OVERVIEW OF NEEDS-BASED SUPPORT ACTIVITIES PILOT PHASE - 1ST CYCLE STADIEM INNOVATION PROGRAM

Activity	Time
Kick-off Pilot Event	7 June
Kick-off Mingling Event	7 June
IBC	9-12 September

TABLE 11: OVERVIEW STADIEM ORGANIZED SHOWCASING AND NETWORKING ACTIVITIES PILOT PHASE - 1ST CYCLE STADIEM INNOVATION PROGRAM

3.2.2 Needs-based support and follow-up

During the Pilot Phase, each start-up/scale-up was assigned a mother hub, which throughout the phase assisted with coaching, follow-up, and served as the main point of contact for the start-up/scale-up. The mother hubs provided their start-ups with individual check-ins and follow up meetings based on the individual needs and wants of the start-up/scale-up. In addition to the check-ins, the mother hubs also facilitated business and investor introductions with companies in their networks based on the needs and requests for each start-up/scale-up.

Activity	Time	Description
Status Meetings	By appointment	Individual check-in meetings between scale-up and mother hub. Need-based.
Business Introductions	By appointment	Demand-based + cross-hub approach
Investor Meetings	By appointment	Demand-based + cross-hub approach

TABLE 12: DESCRIPTION NEEDS-BASED SUPPORT ACTIVITIES PILOT PHASE - 1ST CYCLE STADIEM INNOVATION PROGRAM

3.2.3 Networking and showcasing activities

As one of the objectives of the Pilot Phase is for the start-ups to demonstrate their results and achievements from their STADIEM project at a large scale to a wider community of stakeholders, the STADIEM consortium organized two demo days for the start-ups, in addition to an industry mingling event. The goal of these events was to showcase the start-ups and their demos to an industry audience, to strengthen the STADIEM community, and for them to make new connections.

To kick-off the Pilot Phase, the start-ups were invited to Bergen to join MCB's annual media and media tech festival: Future Week. Here, MCB organized a hybrid showcasing event and a mingling event. Three of the start-ups: Zazu, Trensition, and Tinkerlist, presented their solutions live on stage, while Filmchain joined and presented virtually. The event was also streamed and recorded for the ones that couldn't attend in person. There were about 30+ in-person attendees at the event from the Norwegian and European media industry. The same evening as the showcasing event, the Pilot Phase start-ups joined a mingling event with 80+ attendees, including members from the STADIEM consortium, the start-ups from Match Phase in the second cycle, and members of the Norwegian and European media industry.

The second Demo Day activity was organized at IBC2022. IBC (The International Broadcasting Convention) is one of the world's most influential media, entertainment & technology trade shows for professionals engaged in creating, managing, and delivering entertainment and news content worldwide. Every year, IBC attracts over 50,000 senior media and entertainment professionals from across the broadcasting and content creation world with representatives from over 150 countries. As the Demo activity in the Pilot Phase, the start-ups were invited to exhibit their company and pilot at one of the STADIEM pods at a shared stand with MCB at IBC. The pod was shared between the three start-ups which accepted the invitation to exhibit at IBC: Zazu, Tinkerlist, and Trensition. Tinkerlist had a stand of their own in a different hall of the exhibition in addition. Zazu eventually couldn't make it to the conference due to logistical challenges on their travel day, including a train strike in the Netherlands. The fourth start-up, Filmchain, decided to decline to offer as the exhibit didn't have a strong overlapping target market for the FilmChain solution, and rather focused on attending more industry specific events with their target audience.

The STADIEM pods at IBC attracted not only other start-ups interested in the programme but also Media corporates (EU-based and international) interested in the solutions from both OC1 and OC2 start-ups, as well as some considering joining as a corporate partner in future endeavours. STADIEM was also showcased within partner EBU's booth at IBC, which carried the project's promotional material to inform and connect with the broader broadcasting community, which is the cornerstone of the event.

As one of the main activities in the Pilot Phase were for the start-ups to disseminate their pilots and results, they also initiated and organized for dissemination and event participation themselves. Here is an extract of some of their activities:

- In addition to exhibiting at the STADIEM pod at IBC, Tinkerlist had their own stand at IBC. Here, they demonstrated their pilot in front of a live audience, both streamed online and live at their booth.
- Zazu published demo on their website, where users can test the solutions live for free. Roularta's innovation team attended various conferences and events and talked -

among other things - about the positive collaboration with Zazu within STADIEM and about the automation feature the two teams developed.

- Trensition launched a media campaign to attract new customers, created a landing page on their website, and had two customer cases.
- FilmChain participated in three key events: Kinnernet in France and Unchain Fintech Festival in Romania and Pirate Summit in Germany. FilmChain pitched in front of investors and fintech industry leaders from Central and Easter Europe and won the festival Big Prize - was the Startup Winner out of 24 fintech companies that pitched at the event.

In addition to the Demo Days, the STADIEM consortium and partners also disseminated about the pilots through blog posts and newsletters. VRT also presented the start-ups and their pilots at a Sandbox Hub meeting. The Sandbox Hub is a network in Future Media Hubs, designed to inspire and support international media organisations to collaborate with start-ups/scale-ups. The participants of the Sandbox Hub meetings are media corporations, accelerators, and innovations ecosystems from across Europe.

Activity	Time	Description
Kick-off Pilot Event	7 June	All four scale-ups present their solution on stage in front of a live audience. Organized as part of Future Week 22. Location: Bergen, Norway.
Kick-off Mingling Event	7 June	We're kicking off the final phase of your STADIEM journey together with the new scale-ups in the Match Phase, who've just started their journey. Location: Bergen, Norway
IBC	9-12 September	The closing event of the open call to showcase all the successful pilots that have come through the projects four phases. The start-ups exhibit their pilots to the audience at IBC.

TABLE 13: DESCRIPTION STADIEM ORGANIZED SHOWCASING AND NETWORKING ACTIVITIES PILOT PHASE - 1ST CYCLE STADIEM INNOVATION PROGRAM

3.2.4. Upskilling and training

With the Pilot Phase is the fourth and final phase, the STADIEM consortium decided it best to leave the STADIEM organized training sessions to the preceding phases of the programme. This was because we wanted to prepare the start-ups for their pilots ahead of the pilot being live, and to let them focus on the activities of the Pilot Phase during its duration. Some of the start-ups nevertheless decided to engage in some training activities on their own initiative. Zazu organized several workshops and trainings in collaboration with their corporate partner,

to educate the users of their software. The Tinkerlist team read multiple books to further educate themselves on topics like hacking growth, predictable revenue, and never split the difference.

3.2.5. Evaluation process

Similar to the preceding phases, the Pilot Phase had a proposal, mid-term evaluation and final evaluation. Differing from the other phases, the Pilot Phase didn't have a selection process, as it was the last phase of the programme for the start-ups, and no new phase for them to proceed to.

To successfully accomplish the Pilot Phase, the following requirements were to be fulfilled by each start-up/scale-up:

- Start-up/scale-up presents needs and action plan for the stage at the start of the phase (Annex VI);
- Customer and stakeholder feedback;
- Assessment in form of market impact, collaboration, and further monetization possibilities;
- Execute a successful public pilot;
- Generate new business/investor/client leads.

The evaluation process of the Pilot Phase consisted of the following steps and procedures:

Pilot Phase Proposal: The start-ups had to submit a Pilot Phase proposal at the start of the phase, outlining their plans, objectives, and budget for the phase. The details of this proposal, mainly the budget, determined the pay-out of the first instalment of the Pilot Phase.

Mid-term Review: Mid-way through the phase, each start-up had an individual mid-term review meeting with their assigned mother hub. During this meeting, the mother hub asked and noted down the answers to a set of pre-defined questions on the start-ups collaboration, progress, and results so far in the phase.

There was designed a Mid-term Review Protocol detailing the process of the review to ensure that each hub followed the same approach. The objective of the mid-term review was to map and assess the progress of each start-up. Following the mid-term review meetings, the start-ups had to submit a light financial review report (Annex VIII), to report on their expenses thus far in the phase. The combined review steps determined the payout of the second instalment of the phase.

Final Review: The goal of the final review was twofold. (1) To have a look at the progress the start-ups made during the Pilot phase and the whole STADIEM programme, and to assess their results from the project. (2) To determine whether the consortium could proceed with the payment of the third and final instalment of the Pilot Phase.

As part of the evaluation, each start-up had to submit a report detailing its progress in the Pilot Phase, its results from the programme, feedback on the programme, and its financial review

of expenditures and costs from the Pilot Phase (Annex VIII). They had to submit the second part of this report, the expense report, after the phase had ended to include all occurred costs in the phase.

As with the previous phases, the final step of the Final Review was an Investment Committee Meeting where the start-ups presented their project and achieved results in the pilot phase and in the project in total, while the Corporate presented their assessment and achieved value from the project. The Investment Committee meeting was a meeting with the four innovation hubs of STADIEM (VRT, STK, NMA & MCB), the four selected scale-ups in the Pilot Phase (Trenstion, Zazu, Tinkerlist, FilmChain), their corporate partners, and Investment Committee members. The Investment committee members of this ICM, were three external experts who had been involved in previous selection processes earlier in the programme.

Each scale-up was provided a timeslot of 25-30 minutes. As the Pilot Phase marks the end of these start-ups' participation in the STADIEM programme and there is no following phase, the Investment Committee members did not score the pitches. The Investment Committee's role was to ask any questions they might have and provide feedback on the startups' journey and results.

After the evaluation and phase had ended, each start-up received a letter of recommendation signed by each partner of the consortium.

Activity	Time	Description
Submittal of Pilot Phase Proposal	10 June	<p>The scale-ups will have to submit a Pilot Phase Proposal outlining their plans and objectives for the Pilot Phase.</p> <p>The template will be distributed after acceptance into the Pilot Phase.</p> <p>The Pilot Phase Proposal determines the pay-out of the first instalment of the Pilot Phase financial contribution.</p>
Mid-term Review Meeting	18-22 July	<p>Individual meetings between mother hubs and the scale-ups.</p> <p>Each scale-up present their progress of the first half of the Pilot Phase.</p>
Mid-term Financial Review	22 July	<p>Each scale-up submits their financial review of expenditures and costs from the Pilot Phase this far.</p> <p>The mid-term review determines the pay-out of the second instalment of the Pilot Phase financial contribution.</p>
Evaluation Period	September	<p>Final evaluation and assessment in terms of market impact, collaboration with corporate partner(s), and further monetization possibilities of the scale-ups projects.</p>

Submittal of Evaluation Report Part 1	15 September	See evaluation report template. The evaluation report determines the pay-out of the third instalment of the Pilot Phase financial contribution.
Investment Committee Meeting	28 September	One joint meeting with the four innovation hubs, the four selected scale-ups, their corporate partners, and Investment Committee members. Scale-up presents their project and achieved results in the pilot phase and in the project in total. Corporate presents their assessment and achieved value from the project.
Submittal of Evaluation Report Part 2	3 October	Each scale-up submits their financial review of expenditures and costs from the Pilot Phase this far. The evaluation report determines the pay-out of the third instalment of the Pilot Phase financial contribution.

TABLE 14: DESCRIPTION EVALUATION PROCESS ACTIVITIES PILOT PHASE - 1ST CYCLE STADIEM INNOVATION PROGRAM

3.3 BUDGET AND REIMBURSEMENT

The maximum financial contribution for the Pilot Phase is €50.000 per start-up. 30% of the requested contribution was paid to the start-ups upon approved budget after being selected in the Pilot phase. Should a start-up's Pilot phase budget (requested contribution) exceed the maximum allowed financial contribution of € 50.000 for this phase, the calculation will be 30% of the maximum allowed € 50.000.

The remaining 70% of the requested contribution are reimbursed in two instalments after successful delivery of the KPI's and objectives defined in the Pilot phase plan. This means that the reimbursements of the remaining contribution will be based on actual deliverables, mid-way through the Pilot phase and at the end of the Pilot phase. For the Mid-term review and the final evaluation report, the start-ups must deliver a report of their financial review, indicating costs and expenditures.

The payment depends on the positive assessment of the start-up's Pilot phase activities. The budget should always mirror the start-up's acceleration and upskilling in light of the STADIEM objectives. It may be spent on e.g.,

- Dissemination and promotion activities and materials
- Travel and accommodation expenses related to the main activities in the Pilot Phase
- Tickets to attend conferences and events in line with the objectives of the Pilot Phase
- To develop additional capacities
- To follow workshops and training relevant to the phase

After assessment and acceptance of the final evaluation report by the STADIEM hubs (Annex VII and Annex VIII), the necessary steps for reimbursement will be taken, following VRT's rules for reimbursement. If a start-up does not meet the Phase's expectations or shows signs of negligence, reimbursement will be adjusted accordingly or cancelled altogether.

The table below shows the distribution of the budget according to the GA and Guide for Applicants OC1 and the actual distribution based on the Pilot Phase Proposal (Payment 1) and the financial reports at mid-term (Payment 2) and final review (Payment 3). It shows that the 4 beneficiaries in total consumed **199.998 euro**, hence, with a difference of only 2 euro, **100%** of the foreseen total grant of 200.000 euro.

	Payment 1 30%	Payment 2 35%	Payment 3 35%	Total Period
GA + Guide for Applicants	60.000€	70.000€	70.000€	200.000€
Actual 3rd Party Payment	59.999,4€	69.999,30€	69.999,30€	199.988€
Difference GA - Actual 3rd Party Payment	0,60€	0,70€	0,70€	2€

TABLE 15: OVERVIEW BUDGET AND GRANT DISTRIBUTION PILOT PHASE - 1ST CYCLE STADIEM INNOVATION PROGRAM

3.4 KPI'S AND RESULTS

The main KPI of the Pilot Phase was the selection of at least 4 start-ups/scale-ups to start the Phase. The four top-performing start-ups from the Integrate Phase (Zazu, Transition, Tinkerlist, Filmchain) were invited to and accepted the invitation to the Pilot Phase. All four start-ups completed the phase, and met the expectations of the phase, leaving four successful executed public pilots.

One of the main objectives of the phase was for the start-ups to disseminate about their pilots, generating interest from relevant stakeholders. Three of the start-ups reported having generated 1-12 new business leads during the Pilot Phase. Business leads was in this case defined as potential new partners, re-sellers or similar. All four start-ups reported having generated new investor leads (1-15), and client leads (2-150) generated in the same four-month period. From the table below, one can see that there's some variations in how many leads were generated per start-up in this phase. This can be largely attributed to three factors: (1) The start-ups solution: some had solutions with a larger target audience than others. (2) The start-ups starting point: Some, like Trensition, were venturing into an unknown market, the media industry, while others, like Tinkerlist, had been providing solutions to the media industry for several years. (3) The start-ups strategy: Some of the start-ups, like Zazu, were looking for investors, while others, like Trensition, had secured an investor in the period. Some focused heavily on generating leads, while others focused more on the pilot itself.

Start-up	Business Leads (potential new partners, re-sellers, etc.)	Investor Leads	Client Leads (potential new customers)
Zazu	1	14	9
Tinkerlist	12	3	150
Filmchain	3	15	8
Trenstition	0	1	2

TABLE 16: OVERVIEW LEADS GENERATED BY BENEFICIARIES IN PILOT PHASE - 1STE CYCLE STADIEM INNOVATION PROGRAM

3.5 DEVIATIONS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS

No deviations of gravitas had to be made during the Pilot Phase of the first cycle.

3.6 LEARNINGS

Overall, the different activities of the framework of the pilot phase worked well in practice as planned. However, after the pilot phase was concluded and assessed, several opportunities for adjustments to make for a more frictionless experience for the start-ups of the second cycle of the programme, for example to make them start their Pilot Phase Proposal before the phase starts, and by streamlining the reporting even more, leaving more time for the start-ups to focus on the piloting and dissemination. Some dates in the framework were adjusted during the phase, for example the submission of the proposal, which deadline was extended by a few days.

The pilot phase's timing is less than ideal, as there are very few events happening during the holiday season (June-August), whereas many events are happening in spring and fall, though outside the scope of the phase. This will continue to serve as a challenge for the second cycle as that is to be in the months of May till August 2023.

During this phase the start-ups are supposed to show their product publicly and cause attraction for customers, funds, and investors. To support, STADIEM creates opportunities for the start-ups to showcase their pilot projects. However, to organize an event of impact was challenging, and therefore was timed at the very start and end of the phase, outside the holidays. A lot of events start too soon after the beginning of the phase, so they no longer have a possibility to reserve tickets and plan for attending, the start-ups only know shortly before the phase starts if they're accepted/invited or not.

As with the integrate phase, it was challenging to manage two phases of two different cycles simultaneously, in respect to the resources and capacities for the partners. With two open calls being managed by the same team at the same time, evaluations and events are happening parallel to one another, it doesn't leave any capacity to be spared. As the Pilot Phase only has four start-ups in the programme, one to be supported by each hub, this challenge was less imposing during this phase compared to the Integrate Phase.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This report has provided a detailed overview of the activities of the Integration and Pilot Phases of the first cycle of the STADIEM Innovation Program that took place from March to September 2022. To conclude this deliverable, we present first the main outcomes and results and then highlight lessons learned for improving the Integrate and Pilot Phase in the 2nd Cycle of the STADIEM Innovation Program that will take place from February till September 2023.

Outcomes and Results

On the level of KPI's for both phases, STADIEM managed to achieve the set targets.

At least 12 beneficiaries from the Develop Phase of the first cycle were selected to the Integrate Phase and at least 12 could integrate technically and/or service level their solution with the corporate in order to be ready for a public pilot. This is demonstrated by the submission of 12 final review reports at the end of the phase as well as participation in the remote expert evaluation taking place in the final review process. Two of the 12 beneficiaries declined a selection for the Pilot Phase shortly before the pilot selection meeting of the ICB. In the case of OnHertz a bad timing of public piloting within the STADIEM program compared to other plans of both corporate and beneficiary was perceived. In the case of Utelly, a STADIEM beneficiary was acquired by another company and lost in this way its SME status, which made it ineligible to continue the STADIEM trajectory.

For the Pilot phase OC1, the STADIEM project managed to select and let start 4 beneficiaries from the 10 beneficiaries that declared to candidate for the public pilot phase and at least 4 of them have set up public pilot executions. Due to these public pilots, the four beneficiaries managed to acquire new business leads, investor leads, and client leads. They participated, besides the STADIEM organised demo-event, at various events ranging from IBC (Tinkerlist boot) to Kinnermet to Fintech Finland (e.g. FilmChain won the trophée at Finnish Fintech pitch event) to also launching media campaigns (Trenstition) to showcasing the demo on websites (e.g. Zazu), allowing customers to discover and experiment with the solution.

The exit of Utelly in the Integrate Phase also proves that STADIEM as a program and intervention has had a beneficial impact for the European start-up/scale-up focussing on the media sector since. After FanSifter in February 2023, this the 2nd exit of a STADIEM beneficiary from the first cycle. In both cases, the beneficiaries testified that STADIEM support and development were crucial steps towards generating the exit.

Besides the two exits, the overall result of the first cycle of the STADIEM Innovation Program at the end of September 2022 is that for each 4 phases all KPI's of minimum participation at the beginning of the phase and minimum selection at the end of the phase were always met. During the whole trajectory of the first cycle, there was never a breach in cooperation between a corporate and a beneficiary that would end cooperation during a phase prematurely and force the start-up/scale-up to not apply for the next phase.

Budget and grant distribution

On a budget level, we see that for both cycles the foreseen budget was almost consumed totally (99% in the case of Integration; 100% in the case of Piloting).

Running the program

Thirdly, on an operational level, we see that the project managed to organise two qualitative cycles. The program framework had in both phases an intense rhythm, which allows to keep a steady pace in the innovation track and enable the start-up/scale-up to engage its corporate in the process actively. Mother hubs provided relevant support and mentoring based on individual needs of the beneficiaries and facilitated leads in their networks. Training in the Integration Phase was organised at the beginning of the Phase to let the beneficiaries be fully aware of the importance of the activity, while in the pilot phase STADIEM organised events to showcase the demos of the 4 final beneficiaries (Future Week) and to provide other opportunities for demonstration the solutions (IBC2022). Besides these STADIEM events, the four pilot beneficiaries also took themselves initiatives with their grant to showcase the solution at relevant venues in Europe.

Learnings and future perspective

While the STADIEM Innovation Program thus generated qualitative results both in terms of outcomes, budget and grant distribution, and in terms of running the program, this does not mean that there are no lessons to be learned to improve the program for the 2nd Cycle. The report has also identified for each phase areas for improvement:

The Integrate phase of the second open call had several opportunities for improvement in four categories: timeline, training, finances, and evaluation of the start-ups. The Integrate phase was too short, leading to an intensive period for the start-ups, hubs, and consortium, and there was an overlap with another phase. The start-ups had limited time for training, and deviations in spending were expected in the next cycle. Feedback from external experts helped improve the evaluation process and reporting procedures for a more efficient process in the next cycle.

The pilot phase of the program worked well overall, but there are opportunities for improvement in the next cycle, such as streamlining the reporting process and starting the Pilot Phase Proposal earlier. The timing of the pilot phase during the holiday season is less than ideal and organizing events to showcase the start-ups' products was challenging. Managing two phases of two different cycles at the same time is also a challenge, but this was less imposing during the pilot phase due to a smaller number of start-ups.

These will be incorporated mainly in the 2nd cycle of the Integration and Pilot Phase. To prepare these two phases, already preparatory meetings have been organised within the STADIEM consortium (Hamburg, August 2022 and online, November 2022). This will be reported in the next deliverable D4.4 due in September 2023.

ANNEX I – TEMPLATE PROPOSAL INTEGRATE TO PILOT

FROM INTEGRATE TO PILOT

SUBMIT VIA AIRTABLE BY 8 JUNE 2022 AT 16:00 CEST

Grant Agreement No.: 957321

Call: H2020-ICT-2018-2020

Topic: ICT-44-2020

Type of action: IA

WWW.STADIEM.EU

INSTRUCTIONS

EXPECTED RESULTS

To successfully accomplish the Pilot Phase, the following requirements should be fulfilled by each start-up/scale-up:

- Start-up/scale-up presents needs and action plan for the stage at the start of the phase
- Customer and stakeholder feedback
- Assessment in form of market impact, collaboration and further monetization possibilities
- Execute a successful public pilot
- Generate new business/investor/client leads

Please read the **Pilot Phase Framework** (Available in Airtable) **thoroughly** before writing your proposal. The budget and all activities must be aligned with the objectives and expectations of the phase, outlined in the Framework.

STYLISTIC REQUIREMENTS

- Delete the guidance text in blue in each section.
- There's no maximum page count for this report, but we recommend that you keep it relatively short.
- Proposals should be submitted in PDF format.
- All relevant information should be included in this proposal, refer from linking to other separate documents.

1 OBJECTIVES AND AMBITION

- Briefly describe the objectives of your proposed work and activities in the Pilot phase.
- Briefly describe the main results you want to achieve in the Pilot phase.
- Briefly describe how you expect the activities in the Pilot Phase to impact your innovation capacity.
- Briefly explain the core technology or product you will pilot and the designated clients (in particular or client types).

2 SUMMARY OF PATHWAY TO IMPACT

- Describe the impact you aim to achieve for both you, the scale-up, and your corporate partner in the Pilot Phase.
- Provide a brief description on how you will collaborate with your partner in order to achieve this impact. Who will be involved in the decision-making and how? Who will be taking on what tasks in relation to the proposed objectives and ambitions in order to meet the expectations of the phase?
- Describe what kind of stakeholders you aim to engage in this phase (investors, clients) and how you aim to engage them. (e.g. how do you plan to utilize acquired knowledge, and resources for internal processes such as acquiring more clients, leads, building VC connections and so forth).

3 SUMMARY OF IMPLEMENTATION

Detail your foreseen action plan for the Pilot Phase and describe how your planned activities will enable you to deliver on the objectives of the Pilot Phase. Include:

- A short and clear **timeline / overview of the work plan**, the timing of the different tasks using a Gantt chart or similar
- A detailed **work description / work plan**
- **Deliverables**
- **Milestones**
- **KPI's**
- **Personnel efforts**
- **Budget** (see template below). Justify subcontracting if there is any. Give an indication of in-kind contributions, both from the scale-up and the corporate. Take into account that the reimbursement of costs depends on the deliverables and will be allocated against deliverables, KPI's, and milestones.
- **Risk assessment and mitigation plan**
- **Training / workshops / events** that could help you reach your goals better / more efficiently
- **Communication, dissemination, and outreach plan** you will deploy during the Pilot phase. Keep in mind that all communication activities about the project should correctly refer to STADIEM as European project accepted under the Horizon 2020 framework programme.

Provide enough quantitative detail to justify the proposed resources to be allocated so that progress can be monitored and understood by a relevant business executive from an industry that may or may not be familiar with your particular technological solution or product.

	Month 1	Month 2	Month 3	Month 4	Total
Personnel costs					
Equipment					
Consumables					
Training					
Travel					

<i>Subcontracting</i>					
<i>Total in EUR</i>					

ANNEX II – INTEGRATE FRAMEWORK

INTEGRATE PHASE

14th March 2022 – 13th May 2022

TABLE OF CONTENTS

OVERALL EXPECTATIONS.....	3
PROGRESS MEETING.....	4
BUDGET AND REIMBURSEMENT.....	5
TIMELINE: INTEGRATE FRAMEWORK.....	6
TIMELINE:NEEDS-BASED SUPPORT.....	7

1 OVERALL EXPECTATIONS

1.1 ACTIVITIES

Guide for Applicants, p. 27.

The Integrate phase is a phase where Start-Up/Scale-Ups begin the technical or procedural integration or testing, or pre-Pilot activities for public Pilots. This includes but is not limited to internal testing and evaluation of business processes and performance, technologies, and solutions, components that enable and drive forward the Start-Up/Scale-Up and Corporate collaboration, as well internal and non-public Pilots. Relevant documentation of the integration and collaboration procedures, including integration and Pilot roadmap, APIs, testing and Pilot scoping documentation and evaluation + test and/or Pilot cases is created”.

1.2 EXPECTED RESULTS

During the Integrate Phase, the following requirements should be fulfilled by each Start-Up/Scale-Up:

- Start-Up/Scale-Up presents needs action, and budget plan for the stage at the start of the Phase.
- Start-Up/Scale-Up defines the Budget funding/upskilling for the Phase.
- Start-Up/Scale-Up prepares a *project plan for a publicly accessible and evaluable Pilot including budget, and Pilot readiness checklist with risk assessment.*

- The proposed public Pilot plan meets the needs of the Corporate and the *Corporate confirms the readiness for publicly accessible and evaluable Pilot* (validated by the Corporate through written evaluation form).
- Assessment of plan for the Pilot phase .

Specifically the documentation should include but are not limited to the the following:

- Internal testing and evaluation of **business processes and performance**, technologies, and solutions that enable and drive forward the Startup and corporate collaboration.
- Documentation of the integration and collaboration procedures, including integration and pilot roadmap, APIs, testing and pilot scoping documentation and evaluation (if relevant)
- Detailed description of test and pilot cases(s)
- Corporate validation to the proposed activities with clearly identified and comprehensible feedback about the pilot and its impact and implementation on behalf for the corporate.

As a definition, A 'demonstration or pilot' aims to validate the technical and economic viability of a new or improved technology, product, process, service or solution in an operational (or near to operational) environment, whether industrial or otherwise, involving where appropriate a larger scale prototype or demonstrator.

The evaluation of this Phase will follow three intertwined steps: 1) submission of the project plan for the public Pilot by the Start-Up/Scale-Up2) submission of a written evaluation and confirmation for the public Pilot by the Corporate in the form of an evaluation form 3) pitching session for the STADIEM Investment Committee consisting of at least 3 independent experts and 1 representative per STADIEM Hub.

The Investment Committee then formally approves a list of the top-ranked proposals. Additionally, a mid-term review will take place halfway through the Phase, to check the Start-Up/Scale-Ups' progress in relation to the original needs, objectives and action plan that resulted in their selection for the Integrate phase.

Meeting the criteria does not automatically result in being selected. At least 12 Start-Up/Scale-Ups will be invited for the Integrate Phase, out of which at least 4 Start-Up/Scale-Ups will be selected for the Pilot Phase.

2 PROGRESS MEETING

Halfway through the startups are obliged to prepare and attend an halfway progress reporting meeting to check in and cover the status of their activities during the Integrate phase, and to obtain feedback and if necessary mitigation suggestions from their mother hub.

The startups should present:

- An overview of the implementation the activities performed in the phase including resource spending;
- An overview of impact activities highlighting the actual impact of the co-creation on both start-up and corporate;
- And overview of risk, especially considering the impact to the corporate
- An overview of needs or requests to the mother hub, and / or the consortium.

3 BUDGET AND REIMBURSEMENT

3.1 BUDGET

Budget should always mirror the start-up's acceleration + actual needs (i.e. upskilling, integration or piloting costs) in light of STADIEM.

Tips and tricks to spend the budget:

- To engage specialists / advisors / personnel to guarantee successful co-creation with the corporate, to more effectively manage integration and piloting etc.
- To improve the value proposition or product/solution fit which would increase the value that is brought to the media partner
- Hard investment in R&D
- To develop additional capacities
- To follow workshops and training

Start-up has submitted a budget for the Integrate phase at the end of the Develop phase. During the Integrate Phase, it will be possible to revise the budget in light of actual progress during the Phase, but always in collaboration with and upon approval of the mother hub.

Start-up confirms with the corporate, that the corporate will file in an evaluation form highlighting the work done by the corporate on the project, including confirmation and assessment of the activities to proceed to public pilot, confirmation and assessment of the risks and mitigation actions, as well as the confirmation by the corporate to endorse a public pilot in the Pilot phase.

3.2 REIMBURSEMENT

Start-up will be paid 30% of its Integrate Phase budget of €27.500 upfront at the beginning of the Integrate Phase. When a start-up's Integrate budget exceeds the maximum allowed €27.500 for this phase, the calculation will be of the maximum allowed

The remaining will be reimbursed based on actual deliverables. For the final review the start-ups have to deliver a progress report including a financial review indicating costs and expenditures.

After assessment and acceptance of the progress report by the STADIEM hubs, the necessary steps for reimbursement will be taken, following VRT's rules for reimbursement.

If start-up does not meet the Phase's expectations or shows signs of negligence, reimbursement will be adjusted accordingly or canceled altogether.

4 TIMELINE: INTEGRATE FRAMEWORK

Onboarding meeting + briefing	Week 11 14 March 2022	1 joint meeting with the 4 hubs and the 12 selected start-ups : briefing of expected outcomes, processes and deadlines
Mid-term check-in meeting	Week 15 11 April -15 April 2022	1 meeting per start-up with their mother hub to discuss their progress of the first half of the Integrate Phase
Final review meeting	Week 19 09 May - 13 May 2022	1 meeting per start-up with their mother hub to discuss their progress of the second half of the Integrate Phase
Investment Committee Meeting	Week 21 25 May 2022	1 joint meeting with the 4 hubs, the 12 selected start-ups and the Investment Committee members. Evaluation and ranking based on corporate assessment and pitch / demo
Final Decision Announced	Week 21 26 May 2022	

5 TIMELINE: NEEDS-BASED SUPPORT

Check-ins	By appointment	Individual check-in meetings between start-up and mother hub Depending on start-ups needs
Business introductions	By appointment	Demand-based + cross-hub approach
Investor meetings	By appointment	Demand-based + cross-hub approach

+ Training or Support is available by request to the mother hub considering the short time period of the Integrate phase

+ needs-based training upon approval of mother hub and within € 27.500 start-up budget

ANNEX III – EVALUATION SURVEY INTEGRATE PHASE

Goals

- A methodology to score start-ups' progress in a way that is:
 - clear, scorable, analysable, comparable
 - scoring fairness - scoring is given by: 1) corporate; 2) the evaluator; 3) the consortium's IC
- Enables collecting the feedback, worries, needs by the corporate to build stronger future programs, including STADIEM's OC2
- Collects the data that enables to assess the impact of STADIEM to OC1

NB! Scoring guidelines for evaluators

360° evaluation to assess where the start-ups have got with 8-10 months of funding and support.

- Product readiness
- Suitability & use case
- Biz dev
- Outcomes
- Impact
- Involved staffing
- Budget & resources
- Risks
- Legal
- Data & security
- IP ownership / Co-creation
- SLA readiness
- etc

Assess the growth of the startup's - valuation fundamentals:

- Team size
- Traction
- Product / Market fit
- Large market size
- Delivers true value
- M-to-m growth
- Valuation given by the investors

Corporates should send the questionnaire directly to STADIEM.

Questionnaire to be filled by startup + the corporate

Public	Public	Public		Not public	Not public		C
Area	Start-up questions	Corporate questions	Corporate Score	Weight	Score by the evaluator	Composite Corp + Eval	Score by the consortium
The persona who fills it	Name, position	Name, position, relationship with the start-up's project			Evaluator's name		
Value Proposition (well defined value that the startup delivers)	<p>Write the description of the product the startup is selling: _____</p> <p>What is the problem this product is solving? _____</p> <p>How big is this problem (quantifiable/annualized for this corporate partner? Use appropriate measuring units, e.g., hours saved, etc): _____</p> <p>If the above measuring units were not EUR, please provide the predicted value in EUR/p.a.: _____</p> <p>How does this product solve this problem? _____</p> <p>How much value this solution is predicted to provide (quantifiable/annualized</p>	Same questions	<p>How important is this problem strategically? 1-5</p> <p>How well does this solution address this problem? 1-5</p>		<p>How important is this problem strategically? 1-5</p> <p>How well does this solution address this problem? 1-5</p> <p>Please score if the startup and the corporate have a similar understanding of the product they are buying/selling and the problem they are solving (i.e. the startup has a well-defined value proposition and understands why the corporates will buy their product). 1-5</p>		

	<p>for this corporate): _____</p> <p>If the above measuring units were not EUR, please provide the predicted value in EUR/p.a.: _____</p> <p>How will you measure this value? _____</p> <p>What competitive advantage does this solution provide to the corporate? _____</p> <p>When the startup and the corporate were in the first conversations (May 2021), what was your understanding of the product's readiness. Rate 1-5 (1 = idea / 5 = it seemed to be ready for implementation)</p>						
	<p>How many different corporates have you met to discuss your pilotable product:</p> <p>over the past 3 months: _____</p> <p>meetings booked for the next 2 months: _____</p>	N/A			More meetings = higher score		
Market Size (Startup's value to the society, investors)	<p>How big is the market for this product?</p> <p>How many potential customers in Europe? _____ Globally? _____</p> <p>Describe the ideal corporate customer for this product: _____ (granular attributes of a customer, e.g., industry, company size, job title)</p>	Same questions	How easy or hard do you think it is to sell this product to new customers: 1-5 (5 = easy)		How easy or hard do you think it is to sell this product to new customers: 1-5 (5 = easy)	Large market sizes 1-5 (5 = larger)	

	<p>Name the top 3 corporates that you see as "ideal customers" for this product: _____</p> <p>When beyond the piloting stage, how much do you predict one average customer pays for this product annually? _____ EUR</p> <p>Who are the main competitors to this product/solution? _____</p>						
Learnings and improvements:	<p>List top 3 business-relationship related challenges that could be improved in the future: _____</p> <p>List top 3 business-relationship related lessons learned that could be improved in the future: _____</p> <p>What advice would you give to the startup on what actions it should undertake to improve its business or its business model? Please elaborate: _____</p>	Same questions	Did the startup's team come across as someone who takes the feedback and learns from it: 1-5		Did the startup's team come across as someone who takes the feedback and learns from it: 1-5		
Startup's value growth during the STADIEM programme	<p>Before 01. June 2021:</p> <p>Did the startup receive an investment?</p> <p>Investment size: _____ EUR</p> <p>Valuation: _____ EUR</p> <p>As of [date of this survey]</p> <p>Date of investment (list all if multiple rounds): _____</p> <p>Investment size (list all if multiple rounds): _____ EUR</p>	N/A	No scoring		<p>Higher score for higher mo-to-mo growth: 1-5</p> <p>Higher score for higher assumed current valuation (consider all the attributes in comparison to the other startups): 1-5</p>		

	<p>Valuation (latest): _____ EUR</p> <p>If, then when do you plan to raise investment: _____</p> <p>Approximately how much: _____ EUR</p> <p>As of 01. June 2021:</p> <p>How many non-paying customers the startup had? _____</p> <p>How many paying customers the startup had? _____</p> <p>ARR: _____ EUR</p> <p>Team size: _____ people</p> <p>Of these, how many are in sales (if they have multiple tasks, include if they spend more than 50% of their time in sales): _____</p> <p>As of [date of this survey]</p> <p>How many non-paying customers the startup has? _____</p> <p>How many paying customers the startup has? _____</p> <p>How many pipeline sales leads do you have (with which you are in active conversation)? _____</p> <p>ARR: _____ EUR</p> <p>Team size: _____ people</p> <p>Of these, how many are in sales (if they have multiple tasks, include if they spend more than 50% of their time in sales): _____</p>						
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Did STADIEM provide value and in which way?	<p>The role of the EU-funding:</p> <p>Elaborate: would the startup/corporate partnership have been possible without the EU-funding? _____</p> <p>Describe the top 3 benefits you believe the EU grant enabled the startup to achieve that it would not have achieved otherwise: _____</p> <p>Approximately, how much extra costs did you (startup or corporate) incur with this pilot (e.g., the manhours to integrate, additional development costs, legal fees, etc): _____ EUR</p> <p>Did you hire or engage any additional personnel that you would not have engaged if this pilot would not have happened? _____</p>	Same questions	No scoring		Higher score if STADIEM provided more value to enable a successful startup-corporate partnership: 1-5		
Legals	<p>Legals:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Has the startup finalized the contract negotiations with their corporate partner? ● Do they have a full Service-Level Agreement or an intermediary agreement (e.g. LOI, pre-SLA)? ● Elaborate: how streamlined was the contract 	Same questions	Higher Score for a strong SLA: 1-5		Higher Score for a strong SLA: 1-5		

	<p>negotiation and what have you learned from it?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Does this startup-corporate partnership generate any IP to be created and held jointly? ● Will the startup own the IP and is free to sell it their other future customers? ● Compliance: did the startup or their corporate partner need to build custom solutions to ensure compliance (ex: GDPR or other privacy regulations, data security, etc)? 						
Product Readiness & Success Criteria	<p>Have the parties agreed to clear KPIs and the methodology to measure these before the launch of the pilot that will be used to assess the success of the pilot?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● List the top 3 KPIs: _____ <p>If after the term of the pilot, the KPIs above have been successfully proven, would you be ready to launch this product at full scale? Yes/No</p> <p>Please add how many months from the successful pilot do you estimate it would take to launch the full scale product: _____</p>	Same questions	High score if well-defined success criteria and accountability: 1-5		High score if well-defined success criteria and accountability: 1-5		

	<p>Have the parties assigned the stakeholders and the process to monitor the KPIs?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Please list their titles and roles. 					
<p>Operational & Technical</p>	<p>Did the parties build any custom technical solution to enable this pilot (i.e., not usable for future deployments)?</p> <p>How has the startup and the corporate tested the product prior to the Pilot phase? Please describe: _____</p> <p>How confident are you that, when the pilot is launched, it will deliver the desired outcome? 1-5</p> <p>Explain the approach to the a) systems integration; b) process integration; c) workflow integration:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● were any 3rd party integrators involved? ● How much work (estimated man-days) did the integration required from each party? ● What were the top challenges? _____ ● Which of these has not yet been resolved? _____ <p>If the pilot will be successful, will it likely result in the changes in your current team (hire/fire) to operate the full deployment? (e.g. more people hired to operate the product or</p>	<p>Same questions</p>	<p>Higher score for easier integration and post-integration efforts: 1-5</p> <p>Higher score for higher confidence that the integration's outcome will be positive: 1-5</p>		<p>Higher score for easier integration and post-integration efforts: 1-5</p> <p>Higher score for higher confidence that the integration's outcome will be positive: 1-5</p>	

	service the partnership; people displaced by the product) _____						
Plan vs Reality	<p>What does the actual project plan look like versus the prediction set out in the project plan?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Timeline: prediction versus actual? - Budget: prediction versus actual? - Deliverables: prediction versus actual? 						
Learnings and improvements	<p>List the 3 top challenges related to operational and technical integration aspects that could be improved in the future: _____</p> <p>What advice would you give to the startup on what actions it should undertake to improve its processes or technical approach?</p>	Same questions	Did the startup's team come across as someone who takes the feedback and learns from it: 1-5		Did the startup's team come across as someone who takes the feedback and learns from it: 1-5		
Key Issues	<p>List the key potential risks associated with the Pilot:</p> <p>Risks originating from the startup: _____</p> <p>Risks originating from the corporate: _____</p> <p>How confident are you that the pilot will be launched on [date]? 1-5</p> <p>What are the main potential blockers that might delay the launch?</p> <p>How confident are you that the pilot's results can be assessed by [date]? 1-5</p>	Same questions	Higher Score for a low risk: 1-5		Higher Score for a low risk: 1-5		

	What are the main potential blockers that might delay the assessment?						
Confirmation		Corporate gives a confirmation that they are ready and willing to pilot with this startup on [date range]					

ANNEX IV – MID-TERM TEMPLATE QUESTIONS INTEGRATE

1. your name
2. Company name
3. Your email
4. Mother hub
5. What is your methodology/approach for the Integrate Phase (no more than 1000 characters)
6. How do you define/measure (quantifiable) success for the Integrate Phase (no more than 1000 characters)
7. Please give a short overview of your key planned activities for the phase (no more than 2500 characters)
8. Please give a short overview of the outcomes of these activities for the phase as of midterm (no more than 2500 characters)
9. What key risks have you foreseen/encountered? What have been the corrections/actions?
 - a. Risk 1 – description & as of midterm
 - b. Risk 2 – description & as of midterm
 - c. Risk 3 – description & as of midterm
10. Please list your 5 most important key performance indicators for the phase
 - a. (KPI description & KPI quantifiable unit & KPI target & outcome as of midterm & comment)
11. Please list your 5 most important deliverables for the Phase
 - a. (deliverable description – status – comment)
12. Please give an overview of up to 5 most important working assumptions and their status as of midterm
 - a. (description – planned – outcome)
13. Please describe shortly the status of your timeline and execution of planning (no more than 2500 characters)
14. Please summarize the status of your planned vs actual budget summarized by key categories
 - a. Business development/internal costs: planned, actual, comment
 - b. Technical development: planned, actual, comment
 - c. Marketing and impact: planned, actual, comment
 - d. Consumables: planned, actual, comment
 - e. Travel: planned, actual, comment
 - f. Corporate related: planned, actual, comment
 - g. Other: planned, actual, comment
15. Please upload the overview of your budget in excel or pdf
16. What impact have you generated for your scale-up and your corporate match during the past months? Are you on track? (no more than 1000 characters)
17. What does the collaboration with the corporate company look like (e.g co-creation workshops, meetings, ...)? Is the corporate company committed to the integration? (no more than 1000 characters)
18. What communication activities have you completed in the phase?
 - a. Social media posts (number & comment)
 - b. Conferences (number & comment)
 - c. Newsletters (number & comment)

- d. Webinars/podcasts (number & comment)
 - e. Web articles publications (number & comment)
19. Overview of clients/leads/investors leads?
- a. Business leads (number, comment)
 - b. Investor leads (number, comment)
 - c. New clients (number, comment)
20. What else you'd like to tell us about the Integrate Phase at midterm?

ANNEX V – FINAL REVIEW COST CLAIM QUESTIONS INTEGRATE

1. Name
2. Your company
3. Your email
4. Mother hub
5. Please give a short summary of your start-ups achievements and outcomes in the integrate phase
6. Did you complete your planned activities?
7. Did your three key risks materialize (please list risks and outcomes)
8. Please list your final business development/internal costs in euro
9. Please comment shortly your final budget/spending outcome
10. Please list your final Consumables costs in euro
11. Please list your final Corporate related costs in euro
12. Please list your final Marketing and impact costs in euro
13. Please list your other final Other costs in euro
14. Please list your final technical development costs in euro
15. Please list your final Travel costs in euro
16. Please upload your final budget in excel showing planned and actual costs
17. Please upload your financial proof for costs (invoices etc) all as zipped file (no more than 5 MB in total)
18. What else you would like us to know about the Integrate Phase?

ANNEX VI – TEMPLATE INTEGRATE TO PILOT PROPOSAL

FROM INTEGRATE TO PILOT

SUBMIT VIA AIRTABLE BY 8 JUNE 2022 AT 16:00 CEST

INSTRUCTIONS

EXPECTED RESULTS

To successfully accomplish the Pilot Phase, the following requirements should be fulfilled by each start-up/scale-up:

- Start-up/scale-up presents needs and action plan for the stage at the start of the phase
- Customer and stakeholder feedback
- Assessment in form of market impact, collaboration and further monetization possibilities
- Execute a successful public pilot
- Generate new business/investor/client leads

Please read the **Pilot Phase Framework** (Available in Airtable) **thoroughly** before writing your proposal. The budget and all activities must be aligned with the objectives and expectations of the phase, outlined in the Framework.

STYLISTIC REQUIREMENTS

- Delete the guidance text in blue in each section.
- There's no maximum page count for this report, but we recommend that you keep it relatively short.
- Proposals should be submitted in PDF format.
- All relevant information should be included in this proposal, refer from linking to other separate documents.

1

OBJECTIVES AND AMBITION

- Briefly describe the objectives of your proposed work and activities in the Pilot phase.
- Briefly describe the main results you want to achieve in the Pilot phase.
- Briefly describe how you expect the activities in the Pilot Phase to impact your innovation capacity.
- Briefly explain the core technology or product you will pilot and the designated clients (in particular or client types).

2

SUMMARY OF PATHWAY TO IMPACT

- Describe the impact you aim to achieve for both you, the scale-up, and your corporate partner in the Pilot Phase.
- Provide a brief description on how you will collaborate with your partner in order to achieve this impact. Who will be involved in the decision-making and how? Who will be taking on what tasks in relation to the proposed objectives and ambitions in order to meet the expectations of the phase?
- Describe what kind of stakeholders you aim to engage in this phase (investors, clients) and how you aim to engage them. (e.g. how do you plan to utilize acquired knowledge, and resources for internal processes such as acquiring more clients, leads, building VC connections and so forth).

3

SUMMARY OF IMPLEMENTATION

Detail your foreseen action plan for the Pilot Phase and describe how your planned activities will enable you to deliver on the objectives of the Pilot Phase. Include:

- A short and clear **timeline / overview of the work plan**, the timing of the different tasks using a Gantt chart or similar
- A detailed **work description / work plan**
- **Deliverables**
- **Milestones**
- **KPI's**
- **Personnel efforts**
- **Budget** (see template below). Justify subcontracting if there is any. Give an indication of in-kind contributions, both from the scale-up and the corporate. Take into account that the reimbursement of costs depends on the deliverables and will be allocated against deliverables, KPI's, and milestones.
- **Risk assessment and mitigation plan**
- **Training / workshops / events** that could help you reach your goals better / more efficiently
- **Communication, dissemination, and outreach plan** you will deploy during the Pilot phase. Keep in mind that all communication activities about the project should correctly refer to STADIEM as European project accepted under the Horizon 2020 framework programme.

Provide enough quantitative detail to justify the proposed resources to be allocated so that progress can be monitored and understood by a relevant business executive from an industry that may or may not be familiar with your particular technological solution or product.

	Month 1	Month 2	Month 3	Month 4	Total
Personnel costs					
Equipment					
Consumables					
Training					
Travel					

<i>Subcontracting</i>					
<i>Total in EUR</i>					

APPENDIX VI – PILOT FRAMEWORK

PILOT PHASE

June 2022 – September 2022

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	OVERALL EXPECTATIONS	3
2	EVALUATION REPORT	5
3	BUDGET AND REIMBURSEMENT	6
4	TIMELINE: PILOT FRAMEWORK	8
5	TIMELINE: NEED-BASED SUPPORT	10
6	TIMELINE: NETWORKING AND SHOWCASING EVENTS	11
7	COMMUNICATION GUIDELINES	12

1. OVERALL EXPECTATIONS

1.1 ACTIVITIES

Startups will execute public pilots with the corporate in real-life environments. The pilots are evaluated for generating business value and gathering feedback from customers and other involved parties. The final pilots are assessed in terms of market impact, collaboration, and further monetization possibilities.

The aim of the pilot phase is for the scale-ups and their corporate partners to execute public pilots, demonstrating their results and achievements from their STADIEM project at a large scale to a wider community. This entails that the scale-up must disseminate and demo the pilot publicly. The public pilots can be either client or external consumer focused and must be visible for the public over the course of several months.

Every activity during the pilot phase aims to engage new customers, corporates, partners, endusers, investors, and other stakeholders. The main activities in the pilot phase are to:

Expand: Demonstrate pilot to a wider audience, including prospects similar to the corporate partner.

Promote: Participate in conferences and events, meet with potential users, and disseminate the results of the project.

Invest: Pitch to investors and corporates, collect interest.

1.2 EXPECTED RESULTS

Guide for Applicants, p. 22/23:

Expected results

To successfully accomplish the Pilot Phase, the following requirements should be fulfilled by each start-up/scale-up:

Start-up/scale-up presents needs and action plan for the stage at the start of the phase

Customer and stakeholder feedback

Assessment in form of market impact, collaboration and further monetization possibilities

Execute a successful public pilot

Generate new business/investor/client leads

The evaluation of this Phase will follow two intertwined steps: 1) submittal of a final evaluation report, to be reviewed by the STADIEM Hubs, and 2) a pitching session for the STADIEM Investment Committee, consisting of at least 3 external experts and 1 representative per STADIEM hub. Formal approval by the Investment Committee, unlocks last financing.

Additionally, a mid-term review will take place halfway through the Phase, to check the StartUp/Scale-Ups' progress in relation to the original needs, objectives and action plan, that resulted in their selection for the Pilot Phase.

2 EVALUATION REPORT

At the end of the Pilot Phase, the scale-ups will have to submit an evaluation report, including:

- Summary of Objectives and Ambitions
- Summary of Pathway to Impact
- Summary of Implementation
- Corporate Assessment
- STADIEM Journey

See evaluation report template (to be distributed).

3.1 Budget and reimbursement

3.1 budget

The Budget should always mirror the scale-up's acceleration + skilling/upskilling in light of STADIEM objectives.

Tips and tricks to spend the budget:

- Dissemination and promotion activities and materials

- Travel and accommodation expenses related to the main activities in the Pilot Phase
- Tickets to attend conferences and events in line with the objectives of the Pilot Phase
- To develop additional capacities
- To follow workshops and training relevant to the phase

3.2 Reimbursement

The maximum financial contribution for the Pilot Phase is €50.000 per startup, the payment will depend on a positive assessment of the startup’s Pilot Phase activities.

Startups will be paid 30% of the requested contribution upon approved budget after being selected in the Pilot Phase. When a startup’s Pilot Phase budget (requested contribution) exceeds the maximum allowed financial contribution of € 50.000 for this phase, the calculation will be 30% of the maximum allowed € 50.000.

The remaining 70% of the requested contribution will be reimbursed in two installments after successful delivery of the KPI’s and objectives defined in the Pilot Phase plan. This means that the reimbursements of the remaining contribution will be based on actual deliverables, mid-way through the Pilot Phase and at the end of the Pilot Phase. For the Mid-term Review and the final Evaluation Report, the startups must deliver a report of their financial review, indicating costs and expenditures.

After assessment and acceptance of the final evaluation report by the STADIEM hubs, the necessary steps for reimbursement will be taken, following VRT’s rules for reimbursement.

If a scale-up does not meet the Phase’s expectations or shows signs of negligence, reimbursement will be adjusted accordingly or canceled altogether.

3 Timeline: Pilot Framework

Activity	Time	Description
Onboarding Event	7 June	One joint meeting with the four innovation hubs and the four selected scale-ups. Location: Bergen, Norway

Submittal of Pilot Phase Proposal	7 June	<p>The scale-ups will have to submit a Pilot Phase Proposal outlining their plans and objectives for the Pilot Phase.</p> <p>The template will be distributed after acceptance into the Pilot Phase.</p> <p>The Pilot Phase Proposal determines the payout of the first installment of the Pilot Phase financial contribution.</p>
Mid-term Review Meeting	18-22 July	<p>Individual meetings between motherhubs and the scale-ups.</p> <p>Each scale-up present their progress of the first half of the Pilot Phase.</p>
Mid-term Financial Review	22 July	<p>Each scale-up submits their financial review of expenditures and costs from the Pilot Phase this far.</p> <p>The mid-term review determines the payout of the second installment of the Pilot Phase financial contribution.</p>
Evaluation Period	September	<p>Final evaluation and assessment in terms of market impact, collaboration with corporate partner(s), and further monetization possibilities of the scale-ups projects.</p>
Submittal of Evaluation Report	15 September	<p>See evaluation report template + Each scale-up submits their financial review of expenditures and costs from the Pilot Phase this far.</p> <p>The evaluation report determines the payout of the third installment of the Pilot Phase financial contribution.</p>

Activity	Time	Description
Investment Committee Meeting	28 September	<p>One joint meeting with the four innovation hubs, the four selected scale-ups, their corporate partners, and Investment Committee members.</p> <p>Scale-up presents their project and achieved results in the pilot phase and in the project in total. Corporate presents their assessment and achieved value from the project.</p>

5 Timeline: Need-based support

Activity	Time	Description
Status Meetings	By appointment	Individual check-in meetings between scale-up and mother hub. Need-based.
Business Introductions	By appointment	Demand-based + cross-hub approach
Investor Meetings	By appointment	Demand-based + cross-hub approach

6. Timeline networking and showcasing events

Activity	Time	Description
----------	------	-------------

7 COMMUNICATION GUIDELINES

Kick-off Event	Pilot	7 June	All four scale-ups present their solution on stage in front of a live audience. Organized as part of Future Week 22. Location: Bergen, Norway.
Kick-off Mingling Event		7 June	We're kicking off the final phase of your STADIEM journey together with the new scale-ups in the Match Phase, who've just started their journey. Location: Bergen, Norway
DemoDay		Tentatively scheduled to 9 September	The closing event of the open call to showcase all the successful pilots that have come through the project. More information will follow in July.
Potential events	hub	TBD	The hubs might plan other events during this Phase, if so, more information will follow.

7. Communication guidelines

The announcement of the scale-ups that have been selected for the Pilot Phase is under embargo until the STADIEM consortium publishes the results on their website.

Keep in mind that all communication activities about the project should correctly refer to STADIEM as a European project accepted under the Horizon 2020 framework programme. All communication should mention the following, together with the project name.

If you attend any events outside of the Pilot Phase Framework:

- ➡ Make sure to inform your designated motherhub about your attendance
- ➡ Send your motherhub a photo of your presentation/representation at the event, where the STADIEM logo should be clearly visible

Grant Agreement No.: 957321
Call: H2020-ICT-2018-2020
Topic: ICT-44-2020
Type of action: IA

APPENDIX VII: MID-TERM REPORT PILOT (AIRTABLE)

28-02-2023 11:48

Mid-term Financial Review Report Pilot Phase

Mid-term Financial Review Report Pilot Phase

Deadline: 22 July, 2022, 23:59 CEST.

You are required to fill in all fields in this questionnaire as part of your Mid-term Financial Review Report.

Startup name

<https://airtable.com/shrQE5y2aEA1GVuXy>

1/6

28-02-2023 11:48

Mid-term Financial Review Report Pilot Phase

Your name

Summary of your work

Provide a short summary of your work, activities, and main achievements in the Pilot Phase. Compared to your project plan submitted at the start of the phase. Explain any deviations.

Summary of your progress

Give a short description of your progress this far on reaching your KPIs, Deliverables, Milestones, and other planned activities. Compared to your project plan submitted at the start of the phase. Explain any deviations.

Risks and challenges

List the risks and challenges you have encountered this far in the phase and how you handled/mitigated them.

<https://airtable.com/shrQE5y2aEA1GVuXy>

2/6

28-02-2023 11:48

Mid-term Financial Review Report Pilot Phase

Personnel costs

State your personnel costs that have occurred up to this point in the Pilot Phase (in Euros).

Equipment costs

State your equipment costs that have occurred up to this point in the Pilot Phase (in Euros).

Consumables costs

State your consumables costs that have occurred up to this point in the Pilot Phase (in Euros).

Training costs

<https://airtable.com/shrQE5y2tEA1GVuXy>

3/6

28-02-2023 11:48

Mid-term Financial Review Report Pilot Phase

State your training costs that have occurred up to this point in the Pilot Phase (in Euros).

Travel costs

State your travel costs that have occurred up to this point in the Pilot Phase (in Euros).

Subcontracting costs

State your subcontracting costs that have occurred up to this point in the Pilot Phase (in Euros).

Budget explanation

Explain how the budget has been spent this far. Explain any deviations between planned and actual costs.

<https://airtable.com/shrQE5y2aEA1GVuXy>

4/6

28-02-2023 11:48

Mid-term Financial Review Report Pilot Phase

Upload budget

Upload your budget this far, showing your planned and current costs (see provided budget reporting template).

If you upload a new version, make sure to reflect it in the file name.

 Drop files here

Upload proof of costs

Upload your financial proof of costs (Invoices etc.).

If you upload a new version, make sure to reflect it in the file name.

 Drop files here

Comment (optional)

Is there something you would like to add about your participation and experience in the Pilot Phase this far?

Parent Record ID *

<https://airtable.com/shrQE5y2aEA1GVuXy>

5/6

28-02-2023 11:48

Mid-term Financial Review Report Pilot Phase

IMPORTANT - do not change this record! Let it stay as is, this ID is unique for your company.

Email me a copy of my responses.

Submit

Never submit passwords through this form. Report malicious form

<https://airtable.com/shrQEsy2aEA1GVuXy>

6/6

APPENDIX VIII: FINAL REVIEW REPORT PILOT PHASE (AIRTABLE)

28-02-2023 11:48

Pilot End-of-phase Evaluation Report

Pilot End-of-phase Evaluation Report

Deadlines:

Please note that fields 1.-23. needs to be completed by 15 September (23:59 CET), while the fields regarding the budget and costs (field 24.-32.) are to be completed by 3 October (23:59 CET) to include all occurred costs in the Pilot Phase.

You are required to fill in all fields in this questionnaire.

<https://airtable.com/shrvsRJTpPLhDcmu6>

1/13

28-02-2023 11:48

Pilot End-of-phase Evaluation Report

Please give answers specific to the phase, the whole programme, or both, depending on the field description.

1. Startup Name

2. Your Name

3. Number of Employees in the Start-up

SUMMARY OF OBJECTIVES AND AMBITIONS

4. Summary of Work and Activities

<https://airtable.com/shrsvRJTpPLhDcmu6>

2/13

28-02-2023 11:48

Pilot End-of-phase Evaluation Report

Give a summary of the work and activities performed during the Pilot phase. How did you do compared to your submitted action plan and objectives? (Phase specific)

5. Main Results and Achievements

Give a summary of the main results achieved throughout the Pilot Phase and main achievements in the programme. How did you do compared to your objectives?
(Phase specific and throughout the whole programme)

6. Innovation Capacity

Describe in short, your achieved innovation capacity throughout the programme, a prognosis on how the project has impacted your future innovation capacity, as well as the achieved innovation capacity for your corporate partner.
(Phase specific and throughout the whole programme)

<https://airtable.com/shrvsRJTpPLhDcmu6>

3/13

28-02-2023 11:48

Pilot End-of-phase Evaluation Report

SUMMARY OF PATHWAY TO IMPACT

7. Impact for Start-up

Summary of the impact the Pilot Phase has had for the startup. Include the most important highlights from the whole programme.
(Phase specific and throughout the whole programme)

8. Impact for Corporate Partner

Summary of the impact the Pilot Phase has had for the corporate. Include the most important highlights from the whole programme.
(Phase specific and throughout the whole programme)

9. Collaboration

<https://airtable.com/shrvsRJTpPLhDomu6>

4/13

28-02-2023 11:48

Pilot End-of-phase Evaluation Report

Describe the nature of the collaboration with the corporate, and assess how the collaboration has worked. What went well? What could be improved? Important lessons learned?
(Phase specific and throughout the whole programme)

10. Customer and Stakeholder Feedback

Describe the customer and stakeholder feedback you have collected for the solution(s) you have developed during the STADIEM programme.

11. Assessment

Provide an assessment in form of market impact, collaboration and further monetization possibilities for the solution/product you have developed through the STADIEM programme.

<https://airtable.com/shrvsRJTpPLhDcmu6>

5/13

28-02-2023 11:48

Pilot End-of-phase Evaluation Report

12. Business Leads

How many business leads (potential new partners, re-sellers, etc.) have you generated in the Pilot Phase?

13. Investor Leads

How many investor leads have you generated in the Pilot Phase?

14. Client Leads

How many client leads (potential new customers) have you generated in the Pilot Phase?

15. Customer Acquisition Cost

What is the Customer Acquisition Cost (in euros) of the solution you developed in the STADIEM programme?

<https://airtable.com/shrvvRJTpPLhDcmu6>

6/13

SUMMARY OF IMPLEMENTATION

16. Timeline and Work Plan

Compare your actual timeline with your initial timeline. Explain any deviations. (Phase specific)

17. Deliverables, Milestones, and KPI's

Have you reached the deliverables, milestones, and KPI's as planned in your proposal? Make sure to explain actual progress and any deviations. (Phase specific)

18. Personnel Efforts

Compare your actual personnel efforts with planned personnel efforts. Explain any deviations. (Phase specific)

19. Risks and Mitigation

Describe any risks you encountered during the Pilot Phase and how you mitigated them. Did you have to pivot? Did you encounter any risks you didn't foresee? (Phase specific)

20. Training

Give an overview of the training, workshops, courses, etc. that you have completed in the Pilot Phase. (Phase specific)

21. Communication and Dissemination

Describe your communication, dissemination, and outreach activities in the Pilot Phase (marketing campaign, event attendance, expos, pitching, etc.). What impact did these activities have for your start-up? (Phase specific)

ASSESSMENT

22. STADIEM Journey

This is your opportunity to provide your assessment of the STADIEM programme as a participant. Please see the questions below as a guide on what to include in this part of the report.

How were your experiences throughout the programme and during each phase?

What have you achieved of value from participating and getting this far in the STADIEM programme?

What feedback do you want to provide to the STADIEM consortium?

How could your experience in the programme have been improved?

How will you describe your involvement in the programme?

What could you have done differently to benefit more from your participation in the programme?

(Throughout the whole programme)

28-02-2023 11:48

Pilot End-of-phase Evaluation Report

23. Corporate Assessment

Submit a statement from your corporate partner(s) highlighting their involvement in the activities in the Pilot phase and how the project has created value for them.

(Phase specific)

 Drop files here

FINANCIAL REPORTING

24. Personnel Costs

State your total personnel costs that have occurred in the Pilot Phase (in Euros).

<https://airtable.com/shrsvRJTpPLhDcmu6>

10/13

28-02-2023 11:48

Pilot End-of-phase Evaluation Report

25. Equipment Costs

State your total equipment costs that have occurred in the Pilot Phase (in Euros).

26. Consumables Costs

State your total consumables costs that have occurred in the Pilot Phase (in Euros).

27. Training Costs

State your total training costs that have occurred in the Pilot Phase (in Euros).

28. Travel Costs

State your total travel costs that have occurred in the Pilot Phase (in Euros).

<https://airtable.com/shrvsRJTpPLhDcmu6>

11/13

28-02-2023 11:48

Pilot End-of-phase Evaluation Report

29. Subcontracting Costs

State your total subcontracting costs that have occurred in the Pilot Phase (in Euros).

30. Budget Explanation

Explain how the budget has been spent this far. Explain any deviations between planned and actual costs. Include an explanation of how the budget was spent. Justify subcontracting if there is any. Give an indication of in-kind contributions from the scale-up and the corporate if applicable.

31. Upload Budget

Upload your budget this far, showing your planned and current costs (see provided budget reporting template).

 Drop files here

32. Upload Proof of Costs

<https://airtable.com/shrsvRJTpPLhDxmuf>

12/13

28-02-2023 11:48

Pilot End-of-phase Evaluation Report

Upload your financial proof of costs (Invoices etc.).

📎 Drop files here

Parent Record ID *

IMPORTANT - do not change this record! Let it stay as is, this ID is unique for your company.

Email me a copy of my responses.

Submit

Never submit passwords through this form. [Report malicious form](#)

<https://airtable.com/shrvvRJTpPLhDcmu6>

13/13

